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Table of Contents

1. Document Overview	5
2. Objectives	6
3. Scope	7
4. State of the Art	7
4.1. The Golden Age of Biblical Studies and Computational Technologies	8
4.2. Semantic Analysis of the Greek Bible	10
4.3. Different Approaches to Textual Semantics	11
4.4. Beyond Canon: Multiplicity and Transmission in the Prophetic Tradition and Islamic Exegesis	15
4.5. From Access to Analysis: Digital Resources and Methodological Gaps in Islamic Intertextual Studies	16
5. The New Tool for Intertextual Reference Retrieval	17
5.1. Greek Search Engine Evaluation	17
5.2. Latin Search Engine	21
5.3. Arabic Search Engine	25
6. Methodology	27
7. Findings	28
7.1 Greek and Latin	28
7.2. Arabic	35
8. Conclusion	42
9. Appendix	43
9.1. <i>uBIQUity</i> - Latin and Greek Tool Test (WP8): Feedback Questionnaire	43
9.2. <i>uBIQUity</i> - Arabic Tool Test (WP8): Feedback Questionnaire	84

1. Document Overview

The Ministero dell’Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR)¹ for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Within the structure of the ITSERR project, the Work Package 8 (WP8)–*uBIQUity*, which incorporates the “BI” of the Bible(s) and the “QU” of the Qur’ān in its title, aims at investigating the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam in different environments and historical periods through two huge *corpora*: Greek and Latin Christian commentaries (broadly understood as exegetical works) on the Bible(s) written from the Patristic age until the Late Byzantine period, and classical commentaries on the Qur’ān written in Arabic (*tafāsīr*) from the rise of Islam until the 15th century. These works are unique sources for the study of knowledge, readings, and hermeneutics of the sacred texts through the centuries. The intertextual references, conscious or unconscious, that the ancient commentaries contain work as invisible “places of memory”, making sacred texts “ubiquitous” (hence the title of the project).

By interweaving the research methods of the Humanities and state-of-the-art Computer Science research, *uBIQUity* is developing a novel research tool that can identify references to the Bible(s), the Qur’ān, and the *’ahādīṭ* (the Sayings of the Prophet) in ancient Christian and Islamic exegetical works with a higher degree of accuracy than pre-existing resources.

The WP8 team members are:

- Sara **ABRAM**, University of Palermo (UNIPA): Arabic texts.
- Marcello **COSTA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabrizio **D’AVENIA**, WP8 Leader, UNIPA.
- Cinzia **FERRARA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Anna **MAMBELLI**, WP8 Scientific Coordinator and Product Owner, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE): Greek and Latin texts.
- Chiara **PALILLO**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabio **TUTRONE**, UNIPA: Latin texts.

Regarding research in the field of Computer Science, for the Latin section, the collaboration with the UNIMORE team composed of Davide **CAFFAGNI**, Federico **COCCHI**, Marcella

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), University of Naples L’Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA), and University of Torino (UNITO).

CORNIA, Rita **CUCCHIARA**, and also with Cesare **CONCORDIA** and Carlo **MEGHINI** of the National Research Council (CNR, Pisa) is fundamental. As for the Arabic section of WP8, Giovanni **PUCCHETTI** of the CNR is working on the IT side.

Concerning research and work on Ancient Greek, WP8 has decided to collaborate with the team of another project with similar aims, which has been incubated in the framework of RESILIENCE RI, namely the PRIN (Italian Research Project of National Interest, n. 20229E83B3) *Resilient Septuagint. An Initial Exploration of the Semantics of Killing and Healing in the Septuagint and its Reception in Patristic and Late Antique Sources (3rd cent. BCE-5th cent. CE)*. This PRIN project involves the *Alma Mater Studiorum* University of Bologna (UNIBO, PI Research Unit), the University of Bari (UNIBA), and the University of Catania (UNICT). The *Resilient Septuagint* team members are: Luca **ARCARI** (University of Naples Federico II), Laura **BIGONI** (UNIBO), Laura **CARNEVALE** (UNIBA Research Unit Chief), Davide **DAINESE** (Principal Investigator [PI], UNIBO), Isabella **PIGNOCCO** (UNICT-UNIBO), Arianna **ROTONDO** (UNICT Research Unit Chief and deputy PI), Giorgia **SAMPÒ** (DDC University of Southern Denmark-UNIBO), Gianluca **SCATIGNO** (UNIBO), and Marco **ZANELLA** (University of Padua-UNIBO). This collaboration between WP8 and *Resilient Septuagint* has included and will continue to include the development of a shared methodological framework and interoperable datasets for the study of Greek biblical texts and their heritage.

This document is the third deliverable from the WP8 of ITSERR (D8.1.3) and illustrates the scientific advances enabled by the ***uBIQUity* methodology and software**, drawing on the experience of specialists/testers from the scholarly community. It not only describes *uBIQUity*'s performance in theory (as previously detailed in D8.1.2) but also presents **the results of its “on-field” application**. More specifically, the whitepaper first devotes considerable attention to the state of the art at the intersection of biblical and Islamic studies and digital technologies. The sections titled “The New Tool for Intertextual Reference Retrieval”, “Methodology”, and “Findings” then provide significant and detailed information on the tool and the results of *uBIQUity*'s field operations, showing both the outcomes of user testing and the effectiveness of the algorithms. In doing so, the document highlights the role of the *uBIQUity* platform not only as a prototype but also as a potential instrument for generating new knowledge and opening new avenues of research.

2. Objectives

Building on the project's characteristically fruitful combination of philological methods, computer science, computational linguistics, and design, this whitepaper outlines the current outcomes of the *uBIQUity* platform as an innovative tool that offers (Digital) Humanities researchers advanced LLM(Large Language Model)-based functionalities and a new way of approaching the knowledge produced through intertextual analysis. The textual *corpora* digitized and/or revised and semantically enriched in the earliest stages of the project (see

D8.1.1), together with the User Experience (UX)/Data Visualization Design perspective (as detailed in D8.1.2), provided a solid basis for testing a tool that aims to change the experience of readers of early and medieval Christian and Islamic literatures. Since its very beginning, the *uBIQUity* platform has prioritized a qualitative—rather than quantitative—approach to text comparison, which is reflected in its use of a node-based user interface (UI) designed to manage, display, and compare complex data and metadata across different levels (see D8.2 for further details on the tool’s interface and user interface testing). In this crucial phase, respected experts in early and medieval Christian and Islamic textual traditions have been invited to use and comment on the *uBIQUity* platform, with the main purpose of assessing its performativity, user-friendliness, scientific potential, and accuracy. These tests have ultimately allowed the WP8 team to reassess the platform’s sensitivity to different cognitive learning styles, improving its flexibility and enhancing its potential for innovation.

3. Scope

The project’s interdisciplinary essence—reflected in the integration of the humanities and digital technologies and in its openness to the multilingual nature of religious traditions—has remained a key factor during the testing phase of the *uBIQUity* search engine, which the WP8 IT team developed on the basis of the methodology, digital contents, and tools produced in the earlier stages of the project (see the deliverable D8.1.1). The team of experts in philology, computer science, computational linguistics, and design has played an integral role in the development of the *uBIQUity* platform. At the present stage, their different skills and domains of expertise have been further enriched by the contributions of additional scholars and specialists, selected to provide on-field feedback and to offer a wide range of stimulating questions and comments. Across all roles within the project, there was a shared understanding that evaluating the functionalities of such a complex and multi-layered product as a new semantic search engine inherently requires precise assessment informed by diverse disciplinary perspectives and viewpoints. At the same time, all team members consistently worked to consolidate the various forms of feedback, knowledge backgrounds, and skill sets into a coherent framework, with the aim of providing the Religious Studies scientific community with an agile and innovative digital tool.

4. State of the Art

For scholars of ancient and medieval texts, religious traditions, and intertextuality, computational tools for text reuse detection have become indispensable, allowing for the systematic analysis of vast interconnected *corpora* that would be extremely difficult to examine manually. During the testing phase of the *uBIQUity* platform as a shared repository for Greek, Latin, and Arabic texts, the WP8 research team maintained a constant focus on existing text reuse tools, recognizing them as representing the current state of the art in the field. The primary goal of this awareness was to expand search capabilities in response to

the evolving needs of the scientific community, paving the way for novel approaches to intertextual research through the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and LLMs, and thereby overcoming the known limitations of the tools currently available.

4.1. The Golden Age of Biblical Studies and Computational Technologies

Although it has not yet made a major impact in the AI field, biblical studies represent an area where digital transformations developed early and in a well-structured manner. It is precisely in continuity with these experiences—and with the already established infrastructure for the digital processing of sacred texts—that our project aims to position itself, proposing a possible extension toward integration with AI tools and methods. By biblical studies, we do not refer solely to the contributions of theologians or historians of Christianity.² Rather, we are referring to the most significant results that have emerged from decades of scholarly exchange, research, and collaboration—activities that have, directly or indirectly, revolved around the Society of Biblical Literature since the 1980s.

The initial developments are associated with John R. Abercrombie and date back to the early 1980s, within the broader context of digitizing Greek literary *corpora* for the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae*. The digitization of Rahlfs' 1935 edition of the Septuagint (LXX) highlighted the need to align the Greek text with the Hebrew/Aramaic of the Masoretic Text.³ This led to the CATSS project (*Computer Assisted Tools for Septuagint/Scriptural Study*, 1986), which aimed to create a database preserving every single variant reading of the First Testament in Greek, in addition to the existing alignment, and to provide a morphological analysis of all words in both the LXX and the Masoretic Text.⁴ From a technological perspective, this meant offering texts that were searchable (using a David Packard IBYCUS personal computer), and morphologically analyzed.⁵ From a practical standpoint, the implementation of a straightforward binary algorithm, operating within a word table and a hierarchical tree structure for desinences, proved to be decisive.⁶

² Regarding the digital turn, it is worth noting that theologians have provided an authoritative review of the ethical dilemmas posed by certain issues, particularly those related to digital platforms. This is exemplified by C. Clivaz, “The Bible in the Digital Age: Multimodal Scriptures in Communities,” in T. Hutchings/C. Clivaz (eds.), *Digital Humanities and Christianity. An Introduction*, Berlin/Boston: De Gruyter, 2021, 21–46. This essay also includes a mapping of academic efforts to digitize the scriptural *corpora* of the Jewish and Christian traditions.

³ See E. Tov, *The Greek and Hebrew Bible. Collected Essays on the Septuagint*, Leiden/Boston/Köln: Brill, 1999, 31.

⁴ See <http://ccat.sas.upenn.edu/rak/catss.html>; E. Tov, *A Computerized Database for Septuagint Studies: The Parallel Aligned Text of the Greek and Hebrew Bible*, Stellenbosch: JNSL, 1986.

⁵ In that case, this was made possible thanks to a program David Packard designed in 1973 for IBM Mainframe 390/91 at Nasa's Goddard Flight Center in Washington, DC, as well as the supervision of a team of experts.

⁶ See D.W. Packard, “Computer-Assisted Morphological Analysis of Ancient Greek”, in A. Zampolli/N. Calzolari (eds.), *Computational and Mathematical Linguistics: Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, Firenze: Olschki, 1980, 343–355, on p. 348.

In more general terms, the late 1980s and 1990s were particularly fortunate for computational linguists interested in the sacred scriptures of the Jewish and Christian traditions.⁷ In 1998, CATSS was integrated into Accordance (<https://www.accordancebible.com/>), the second of the so-called biblical software created to handle ancient Greek,⁸ after BibleWorks (<https://www.bibleworks.com/>), developed in 1992 to support preaching and pastoral activities.⁹

Today, the digital landscape of biblical studies offers a wide array of source collections that, from a technological standpoint, focus more on data representation (and knowledge) than on data processing. These platforms manage the copyrights of various dictionaries and editions for a fee, including Olive Tree (<https://www.olivetree.com/>), BibleWorks, Accordance, Logos (<https://www.logos.com/>), Brill Dead Sea Scrolls Concordance (which uses and refines Martin G. Abegg's database—through texts edited by the Oxford series *Discoveries in the Judean Desert*—and now offers it integrated into Brill's Electronic Library:

https://brill.com/display/package/9789004310391?srsId=AfmBOoozmj_Yt77uLHPNEx3M_hBzwnYAsa_glzInrn3pyYj5VAZC609N), or are open source, such as the STEP Bible (<https://www.stepbible.org/>).

⁷ On the Second Testament see: M.E. Davison, “New Testament Greek Word Order”, *Literary and Linguistic Computing* (LCC) 4 (1989), 19–28; H.H. Greenwood, “St Paul Revisited—A Computational Result”, LCC 7 (1992), 43–47, Id., “St Paul Revisited—Word Clusters in Multidimensional Space”, LCC 8 (1993) 211–219; Id., “Common Word Frequencies and Authorship in Luke's Gospel and Acts”, LCC 10 (1995), 183–187; G. Ledger, “An Exploration of Differences in the Pauline Epistles using Multivariate Statistical Analysis”, LCC 10 (1995), 85–97; D.L. Mealand, “Correspondence Analysis of Luke”, LLC 10 (1995) 171–182; Id., “Measuring Genre Differences in Mark with Correspondence Analysis”, LLC 12 (1997), 227–245; A.J.M. Linmans, “Correspondence Analysis of the Synoptic Gospels”, LLC 13 (1998), 1–13; G.K. Barr, “A Computer Model for the Pauline Epistles”, LLC 16 (2001), 233–250; Id., “Interpolations, Pseudographs, and the New Testament Epistles”, LLC 17 (2002), 439–455; Id., “Two Styles in the New Testament Epistles”, LLC 18 (2003), 235–248; A. Wilson, “Developing Conceptual Glossaries for the Latin Vulgate Bible”, LLC 17 (2002), 413–426. On the First Testament it is worth mentioning the third section of the *Historical Dictionary of the Hebrew Language* (see R. Merkin/Z. Busharia/E.Meir, “The Historical Dictionary of the Hebrew Language”, LLC 4 [1989], 271–273) and the application of the famous TUSTEP (*Tübingen System von Textverarbeitungsprogrammen*) to the Book of Daniel (W. Bader [ed.], „Und die Wahrheit wurde hinweggefegt“: *Daniel 8 linguistisch interpretiert*, Tübingen: Francke, 1994).

⁸ Accordance achieved this by merging Bibles from Roy Brown's biblical software, originally ThePerfectWord, later MacBible, and the Dead Sea Scrolls word database created by another Mac-user, Martin G. Abegg. See Tov, *The Greek and Hebrew Bible*, 43.

⁹ Collections of digitized biblical versions and biblical commentaries began to circulate in 1980.

4.2. Semantic Analysis of the Greek Bible

A semantic analysis of the Greek Bible (or the Greek “Bibles,” if we consider the plurality of ancient circulating versions) must be conducted on two levels. The first concerns how the text was reconstructed; the second addresses the coexistence of multiple versions, each reflecting both the individuals who produced it and the broader social and historical context from which it emerged. Both levels are historical in nature but ontologically distinct.

The first level pertains to the event itself: acts such as copying manuscripts or critically reconstructing a text. These events unfold within temporalities measurable in human lifespans, or fractions thereof. Knowledge at this level can often be formalized in binary terms (true/false), represented graphically—as in a *stemma codicum*—and managed by inferential engines.

The second level concerns the *conditions of possibility*, a concept Reinhart Koselleck termed “historical structures.” These possess their own temporalities, which are not commensurable with individual lifespans, spanning everything from the subjectivity of single moments to entire generations.

Between the dimension of the event and that of its conditions of possibility lies a space that cannot be fully formalized in binary terms. The conditions of possibility have an ontological status distinct from actual events: they define what could happen but did not, what remains thinkable, traceable, or reconstructable beyond what actually occurred. Conceptually, they align with Platonic ideas or Aristotle’s notion of the “verisimilar” in his *Poetics*. The range of potentialities encompassed cannot be reduced to simple true/false categories; if an event could have unfolded differently (true), its alternatives do not correspond to a single false counterpart but rather to a potentially infinite spectrum of possibilities.

This logic applies, to some extent, also to texts and the history of their transmission. A critical apparatus that documents different versions of a text can be understood as a trace of its true nature: plural, and deeply dependent on the multiplicity of contexts in which it was copied and in which it has concretely “lived”. These are precisely the issues familiar to scholars of biblical reuse and intertextuality in patristic literature—forms of reuse that may also influence textual reconstruction in cases where manuscript evidence is insufficient. In such instances, the very distinction between true and false proves inadequate, as it imposes a hierarchy shaped by the judgments of the modern editor(s), at the expense of the text’s irreducible plurality. The reality of textual transmission, particularly in sacred *corpora*, is far closer to a continuum of possibilities than to a neat dichotomy. Concepts from fuzzy logic or graded similarity may provide more appropriate frameworks for modeling this multiplicity. Such approaches were explored in early computational semantics and have found renewed applications in contemporary neural networks, but they remain underutilized in the context of ancient texts.¹⁰ Their potential to express proximity, approximation, or even

¹⁰ See L.H. Zadeh, “Text-Score Semantics as a Basis for Computational Approach to the Representation of Meaning”, *LLC 1* (1986), 24–35.

interpretive ambiguity makes such frameworks particularly well suited to the study of biblical intertextuality, where meaning is rarely fixed and consistently embedded in historically situated acts of reception. At the same time, since no one intends to overturn entire valuable philological traditions, information concerning the reconstruction of the text—and the relative primacy assigned to a given version—must also be preserved in the digital environment. For this purpose, the micro-operations linking a critical apparatus to its base text can remain strictly binary.

4.3. Different Approaches to Textual Semantics

As noted in the previous paragraph, referring to the “semantics of natural language” in the context of the relationship between “historical structure” and manuscript production points to a problem that extends beyond the strictly linguistic dimension. It is, rather, inherently intertextual, since the meaning of the biblical text is shaped by its reception. Indeed, the reuse of biblical texts functions not simply as repetition but as re-signification. In ancient Christian literature, biblical intertextuality frequently operates at a semantic level that transforms the source, often in subtle ways. This raises questions that go beyond the surface of textual similarity and concern, instead, the deeper logic of textual plurality—how meaning is transmitted, reshaped, and contextually determined.

This leads us into a broad and, in some respects—within literary studies—autonomous field of research, yet one for which a substantial tradition of digital and computational inquiry already exists and deserves brief consideration. Broadly speaking, two principal approaches may be distinguished, which at various points have either coexisted or alternated over time: the classificatory/ontological approach¹¹ and the text-reuse approach.¹² Alongside these two

¹¹ See most recently J. Horstmann/C. Lück/I. Normann, “Systems of Intertextuality: Towards a Formalization of Text Relations for Manual Annotation and Automated Reasoning”, *Digital Humanities Quarterly* (DHQ) 17 (2023), 1–74; R. Hohl Trillini/S. Quassdorf, “A ‘Key to All Quotations’? A Corpus-based Parameter Model of Intertextuality”, *LLC* 25 (2010), 269–286, who have rejected classifications based on so-called “classic” types that were not grounded in formal logic. Overall, this approach is undoubtedly fruitful, both for constructing digital archives and for ensuring long-term preservation: see T.L. Andrews/C. Macé (eds.), *Analysis of Ancient and Medieval Texts and Manuscripts: Digital Approaches*, Turnhout: Brepols, 2014, particularly pp. 183–244 (i.e. the chapters by L. Spinazzè, S. Rubenson, C. Tupman/A. Jordanous, M. Romanov); G. Tomazzoli, “Intertextuality in Dante’s *Commedia*: Hypermedia Dante Network”, *Bibliotheca Dantesca* 5 (2022), 308–311. To a certain extent, research based on network analysis can be placed within this area: see M. Romanello, “Exploring Citation Networks to Study Intertextuality in Classics”, *DHQ* 10 (2016), 1–46. It is also worth mentioning D. Bamman/G. Crane, “The Logic and Discovery of Textual Allusion”, in *Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Language Technology for Cultural Heritage Data* (LaTeCH 2008) at http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2008/workshops/W22_Proceedings.pdf#page=31.

¹² In this respect, the most successful tool to date remains the text-reuse software TRACER by Marco Büchler, which can be adapted to any type of text (<http://www.etrp.eu/research/tracer/>). Büchler’s PhD thesis provides the most comprehensive overview of text-reuse approaches: M. Büchler, *Informationstechnische Aspekte des Historical Text Re-Use*, Universität Leipzig, 2013.

paradigms, additional computational methods—particularly statistical and distributional techniques—have also been employed. They date back to the late 1990s until 2013 (the year of the transition to predictive models with word2vec), but they can still perform quite well in certain circumstances.¹³

Text-reuse algorithms in particular—descendants of the language-agnostic approaches to machine translation developed in the 1940s—,¹⁴ remain the most widely used technology for intertextual research in Ancient Greek literature, largely due to the implementation of the N-gram function in the latest version of the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* (TLG).¹⁵ These text-reuse tools are technologically classical and reliable, “old-school” instruments that nevertheless pose a philological problem. Even when they allow for complex granularity—enhanced with morphological or semantic annotations—they do not permit the exploitation of information provided by the critical apparatus of the main reference editions. Working exclusively with edited texts, without integrating evidence from manuscript transmission, does not constitute genuine scholarly knowledge. From a technical standpoint, the main strength of these tools lies in their simplicity and robustness: they can efficiently detect literal repetitions across massive *corpora* without requiring extensive linguistic annotation. This makes them particularly suitable for the study of ancient languages, where resources are limited. Indeed, they enable a form of knowledge representation that is modular, explainable, and adaptable. However, their effectiveness is constrained by their reliance on surface forms. N-gram algorithms are highly sensitive to variation: a single morphological or syntactic shift may prevent detection. Furthermore, they fail to capture paraphrastic reuse, synonymy, or stylistic modulation—all of which are central to the ways in which sacred texts were cited, adapted, and transformed in antiquity. In this respect, such methods provide a perspective on intertextuality that is frequently too shallow and reductive.

To address some of these limitations, more complex systems such as TRACER have been developed.¹⁶ TRACER (<https://www.etrapp.eu/research/tracer/>) provides a modular and configurable platform that allows for the combination of multiple metrics—including lexical, structural, and linguistic features—to detect not only literal reuse but also conceptual or semantic similarity. In theory, this enables a more nuanced analysis of intertextual phenomena. In practice, however, TRACER presents several obstacles. Its configuration is

¹³ See S. Stopponi/N. Pedrazzini/S. Peels/B. McGillivray/M. Nissim, “Evaluation of Distributional Semantic Models of Ancient Greek: Preliminary Results and a Road Map for Future Work”, in *Proceedings of the Ancient Language Processing Workshop*, Shoumen: Incoma, 2023, 49–58; T. Köntges, “Measuring Philosophy in the First Thousand Years of Greek Literature”, *Digital Classics Online* 6 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.11588/dco.2020.2.73197>. See also D.M. Blei/A.Y. Ng/M.I. Jordan, “Latent Dirichlet Allocation”, *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 3 (2003), 993–1022.

¹⁴ See W. S. Bennett, “The Place of Semantics in MT Systems”, *LLC* 4 (1989), 200–202.

¹⁵ See T. Sommerschild/Y. Assael/J. Pavlopoulos, “Machine Learning for Ancient Languages: A Survey”, *Computational Linguistics* 49 (2023), 703–747, on p. 723.

¹⁶ Büchler, *Informationstechnische Aspekte des Historical Text Re-Use*.

technically demanding and requires extensive tuning and manual pre-processing, especially when dealing with morphologically rich or historically stratified languages such as Ancient Greek. Moreover, while promising in scope, TRACER still suffers from high rates of false positives, and its performance in complex literary *corpora* remains inconsistent. Critically, for TRACER to function at its full potential, it requires a preliminary linguistic analysis of the texts so detailed that it substantially diminishes the very knowledge gap that the research question on textual reuse was originally intended to address. These limitations are particularly pronounced when applied to biblical or patristic materials, which frequently employ flexible and allusive reuse strategies that resist straightforward algorithmic capture.

A similar set of considerations applies to ontological approaches, such as WordNet—another area of NLP research, conceived by American linguists (most notably George A. Miller) in the early 1980s and still active today¹⁷—or formal knowledge representation models based on OWL and RDF. These systems enable the structuring of lexical items into hierarchies and conceptual domains, offering powerful tools for disambiguation, semantic tagging, and interoperability across *corpora*. The Ancient Greek WordNet, in particular, has aimed to map the Greek lexicon onto semantic fields reminiscent of Dewey decimal classifications, thereby enabling a form of conceptual navigation through the language.¹⁸ Nevertheless, the limitations of such approaches must be acknowledged: ontologies tend to be static and idealized, whereas the meaning of biblical texts is historically fluid and

¹⁷ See C. Fellbaum (ed.), *WordNet. An Electronic Lexical Database*, Cambridge: MIT Press, 1998. Over the years, WordNets have proven effective for word sense disambiguation (cf. E. Agirre/O. López de Lacalle/A. Soroa, “Random Walks for Knowledge-based Word Sense Disambiguation”, *Computational Linguistics* 40 [2014], 57–84; S. Melacci/A. Globo/L. Rigutini, “Enhancing Modern Supervised Word Sense Disambiguation Models by Semantic Lexical Resources”, in N. Calzolari/K. Choukri/C. Cieri *et al.* [eds.], *Proceedings of the Eleventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation [LREC 2018]*, Miyazaki: European Language Resources Association, 2018, 1012–1017), summarization (A.R. Pal/D. Saha, “An Approach to Automatic Text Summarization Using WordNet”, in *2014 IEEE International Advance Computing Conference [IACC]*, Washington, DC: IEEE, 2014, 1169–1173; N. Xie/S. Li, H. Ren *et al.*, “Abstractive Summarization Improved by WordNet-Based Extractive Sentences”, in *CCF International Conference on NLP and Chinese Computing*, Cham: Springer, 2018, 404–415), query expansion (M. Lu/X. Sun/S. Wang *et al.*, “Query Expansion via WordNet for Effective Code Search”, in *2015 IEEE 22nd International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution, and Reengineering [SANER]*, Washington, DC: IEEE, 2015, 545–549; W. Li/S. Wang/Z. Yu, “Deep Learning and Semantic Concept Space Are Used in Query Expansion”, *Automatic Control and Computer Sciences* 52 [2018], 175–183), and clustering (C. Wang/Y. Song/A. El-Kishky *et al.*, “Incorporating World Knowledge to Document Clustering via Heterogeneous Information Networks”, in *Proceedings of the 21st ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, New York: Association For Computing Machinery, 2015, 1215–1224; L. Stanchev, “Semantic Document Clustering Using Information from WordNet and DBpedia”, in *2018 IEEE 12th International Conference on Semantic Computing [ICSC]*, Washington, DC: IEEE, 2018, 100–107).

¹⁸ G. Scatigno, “Analysis of Anachronistic Lemmas and Semantic Fields in Ancient Greek WordNet”, in *Proceedings of the 13th Global WordNet Conference (GWC 2025)*, Pavia: Global Wordnet Association, 2025, 95–99.

contextually contingent. Moreover, current ontological resources for Ancient Greek are still under development and frequently lack integration with editorial practices or manuscript-based variations. Thus, while ontologies are highly effective in modeling possible meanings, they fall short of capturing the actual semantic complexity and historical stratification inherent in scriptural texts. While these limitations remain substantial, recent research has begun to address them by rethinking ontologies not as fixed hierarchies, but as flexible interfaces connected to dynamically annotated *corpora*.

It is worth noting that recent developments in hybrid semantic models—which attempt to combine ontological structures with usage-based *corpora*—are opening new possibilities. Projects such as LiLa: Linking Latin, which focuses on Latin, provide an instructive example: they aim to bridge lexical ontologies with lemmatized textual data, thereby enabling a form of dynamic interaction between lexicon and corpus.¹⁹ In the Greek domain, a similar integration is still in its infancy, but theoretical proposals have begun to emerge that emphasize context-aware ontologies, in which meaning is not only assigned hierarchically but also indexed to syntactic, discursive, and pragmatic information drawn from actual textual instances. Such approaches challenge the traditional divide between lexicon and discourse by treating meaning as both structured and emergent. For biblical texts—whose semantics are shaped as much by reception and reuse as by internal coherence—these flexible ontological models could, in the future, allow for more nuanced representations of concepts such as πίστις (‘faith’), λόγος (‘word’), or δικαιοσύνη (‘justice’), whose semantic load varies significantly across books, genres, and communities.

A tool like BiblIndex, a project led by Sources Chrétiennes – HiSoMA in Lyon, is the only available digital tool that attempts to specifically address biblical intertextuality as a core feature of ancient Christian texts (<https://www.biblindex.org/en>). It is a valuable online index of around 400,000 biblical references (indicated as ‘quotations’ or ‘allusions’) in early Christian literature, including both Western and Eastern texts. However, it does not perform a direct search in the texts but only relies on the biblical passages identified as such by the editors of each patristic work, redirecting to the pages and paragraphs of the printed editions.²⁰

¹⁹ F. Mambrini/F.M. Cecchini/G. Franzini/E. Litta/M.C. Passarotti/P. Ruffolo, “LiLa: Linking Latin. Risorse linguistiche per il latino nel Semantic Web”, *Umanistica Digitale* 8 (2020), 63–78.

²⁰ For the developments of BiblIndex in the last decade, see, in particular, L. Mellerin, “New Ways of Searching with BiblIndex, the Online Index of Biblical Quotations in Early Christian Literature”, in C. Clivaz/A. Gregory/D. Hamidović (eds.), *Digital Humanities in Biblical, Early Jewish and Early Christian Studies*, Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2014, 177–190; C. Crosnier/L. Mellerin, “La constitution des référentiels bibliques du projet BiblIndex”, in G. Bady/M.C.A. Korpel (eds.), *Les délimitations éditoriales des Écritures des bibles anciennes aux lectures modernes/Editorial Delimitations of the Scriptures from Ancient Bibles to Modern Readings*, Leuven/Paris/Bristol: Peeters, 2020, 235–247. We thank Guillaume Bady and Laurence

4.4. Beyond Canon: Multiplicity and Transmission in the Prophetic Tradition and Islamic Exegesis

Just as the semantic analysis of the Greek Bible (or Greek “Bibles”) must account for both the reconstructed form of the text and the coexistence of multiple ancient versions—each rooted in specific historical and social contexts—the same holds true for the study of *ḥadīth* and *tafsīr corpora* and their reception within the Islamic tradition. Across the vast corpus of *ḥadīth* collections and Qur’ānic commentaries, numerous instances occur in which a single prophetic narration appears in multiple, sometimes divergent, forms. These variations may involve not only the wording or phrasing of the *matn* (content), but also the structure of the *isnād* (chain of transmission), the narrative framing, or the interpretive function of the *ḥadīth* itself within a specific exegetical context. Such multiplicity is not a marginal phenomenon; rather, it constitutes a defining feature of these prophetic texts.

It poses methodological challenges which cannot be reduced to binary evaluations of “true” or “false” transmissions. On the contrary, the presence of multiple formulations of a *ḥadīth*—sometimes attested only in exegetical works and absent from canonical or even non-canonical compilations—offers valuable evidence of the richness and historical depth of the prophetic written tradition. These testimonies, though not necessarily part of the most rigorously authenticated collections—compiled according to strict criteria of transmission reliability within the Islamic tradition—, remain critical for understanding how Islamic knowledge was reshaped, transmitted, and interpreted over time. They shed light on the historical, intellectual, and doctrinal environments in which such traditions were reformulated and recontextualized.

This complexity becomes particularly evident when tracing the reuse of individual *aḥādīth* in *tafsīr* literature. The same prophetic report may appear in markedly different formulations—whether abridged, expanded, reformulated, or recontextualized—depending on the exegete’s hermeneutical aims, rhetorical needs, or knowledge. One explanation for this is that, while the *muhaddithūn* (scholars of *ḥadīth* transmission) were committed to codifying only rigorously authenticated prophetic reports, the *mufasssīrūn* (Qur’ānic exegetes) pursued different objectives. They prioritized coherence with the Qur’ānic context and sought clarity and completeness in the interpretation of individual Qur’ānic verses, often citing *aḥādīth* that elaborated upon the Qur’ān’s brevity or made explicit meanings that were only implicit in the Qur’ānic text. Reports with incomplete or absent *asānīd* could still be cited meaningfully, contributing to a broader exegetical narrative. Their use within the *tafsīr* corpus—particularly when they are absent from canonical compilations—may even constitute the only surviving trace of a given tradition.

These variations, far from being editorial inconsistencies or marginal anomalies, attest to the dynamic and dialogical nature of prophetic transmission. They reflect a broader continuum of interpretive and textual practices that cannot be reduced to questions of formal

authenticity. Rather, they offer valuable clues for reconstructing the relationship between the prophetic legacy and Qur’ānic interpretation, as well as for tracing the processes through which meaning was constructed and reshaped over time.

From this perspective, the transmission of the prophetic and exegetical heritage—not only through the reuse of *ahādīth*, but also through the intertextual reworking of *tafsīr* traditions themselves—emerges not as a fixed canon, but as a dynamic continuum: historically mobile, yet consistently grounded in specific exegetical contexts. The plurality of versions and uses is not a flaw to be corrected, but rather an essential dimension to be investigated. Acknowledging this multiplicity does not undermine the integrity of the tradition; instead, it opens new avenues for exploring how meaning was preserved, adapted, and transformed over centuries of Islamic scholarship.

4.5. From Access to Analysis: Digital Resources and Methodological Gaps in Islamic Intertextual Studies

When it comes to the Qur’ān and other foundational texts of the Islamic tradition—such as *hadīth* collections and major works within the *tafsīr* corpus from the 8th to the 15th century—digital libraries and Arabic-language websites (e.g., Shamela and IslamWeb; see D8.1.1) offer an impressive range of accessible resources. From a technological perspective, however, these platforms primarily focus on the digitization and structured presentation of sources rather than on computational processing or semantic enrichment. Many tools, such as Altafsir.com (<https://www.altafsir.com/>) for the *tafāsīr* or Sunnah.com for the *ahādīth* (<https://sunnah.com/>), provide fully searchable texts organized according to their internal divisions (chapters and verses for the Qur’ān; books and chapters for *hadīth* collections). While these platforms facilitate navigation and citation retrieval, they do not yet offer mechanisms for semantic search or intertextual analysis.

Most existing tools rely on literal string-matching or keyword-based search functions. While effective for retrieving exact phrases, they do not support the identification of paraphrastic reuse, conceptual similarity, or stylistic transformation—features that are central to understanding how the Qur’ān and the prophetic tradition have been quoted, adapted, and interpreted over time. In this regard, the limitations observed in Arabic studies mirror those in Greek and Latin: N-gram-based or literal-matching algorithms are highly sensitive to morphological or syntactic variation, and even minimal reformulations can prevent detection. This produces a reductive model of intertextuality that fails to capture the full complexity of historical textual transmission and exegetical practices.

Moreover, the Arabic textual tradition still lacks certain tools that have long been available in other fields, such as a unified, TLG-style environment where texts can be queried, compared, and annotated in semantically rich ways. Widely used platforms like Sunnah.com, despite their accessibility, only allow for surface-level retrieval and do not incorporate mechanisms for identifying intertextual relationships beyond exact matches.

This technological gap becomes even more pronounced when considering the lack of advanced tools for detecting and analyzing text reuse and intertextuality in Islamic religious

texts. No existing resource currently allows for the efficient analysis of intertextual references using methods such as automatic lemmatization of inflected forms, in-depth semantic analysis, or N-gram-based concordance. While tools such as dictionaries, translations, and morphological analyzers are available, they are often scattered across different platforms, rarely updated, and lack integration. This fragmentation severely limits scholars' ability to trace meaningful connections between *tafāsīr* and other genres, particularly the collections of *ahādīth*. Moreover, no single platform currently brings together linguistic support, semantic enrichment, and computational approaches for detecting both literal and non-literal reuse.

An integrated infrastructure combining lemmatization, morphological annotation, and semantic similarity metrics would represent a major advance for Islamic Studies as a whole. It would enable researchers to explore intertextual references with greater precision and to reconsider the methodological frameworks through which Islamic sources are analyzed. The capacity to visualize and interact with a large quantity of data through a user-friendly platform interface would improve accessibility and inclusivity in the field of Religious Studies and support the emergence of new perspectives and analytical approaches.

This scope has guided the WP8 team in developing a rigorous methodology for identifying and analyzing intertextual references, thereby laying the groundwork for a semantic search engine. *uBIQUity* represents a first valuable step toward addressing this gap by exploring the potential of combining morpho-syntactic data and vector-based similarity measures to support the study of textual reformulations in Islamic exegetical traditions.

5. The New Tool for Intertextual Reference Retrieval

5.1. Greek Search Engine Evaluation

To facilitate intertextual research within *uBIQUity*, a search engine dedicated to the Septuagint—the oldest known Greek translation of the Hebrew Bible—has been developed. In this system, the atomic unit of retrieval is the biblical verse, each enriched with historically attested textual variants. The search engine enables both syntactic and semantic search, supporting flexible exploration of textual parallels.

The syntactic component employs language-agnostic string-matching techniques, including common word overlaps, trigrams, and shingles. For semantic search, SPhilBERTa, a transformer-based language model trained on Greek philosophical and theological texts,²¹ was used to generate vector embeddings for each verse and query fragment. These embeddings enable semantic similarity matching beyond literal word overlap.

²¹ See F. Riemenschneider/A. Frank, “*Graecia capta ferum victorem cepit*. Detecting Latin Allusions to Ancient Greek Literature”, in *Proceedings of the Ancient Language Processing Workshop*, Shoumen: Incoma, 2023, 30–38.

To evaluate the system’s performance, test data were provided from humanist WP8 researchers, who identified approximatively 80 intertextual references between selected works of Clement of Alexandria and passages from the Septuagint (for further details on these selected exegetical works, see D8.1.1). For each reference, the corresponding fragment from Clement was used as a query to assess whether the system could retrieve the relevant biblical passage(s) within the top 50 results, ranked by pertinence, a metric commonly known as Success@K or Recall@K.

Three search configurations were tested: syntactic-only search (based on surface string similarity), embedding-only search (based on semantic vector similarity), and hybrid search (combining syntactic and semantic scoring).

In addition, each configuration was evaluated in two modes:

- Full Search, conducted over the entire Septuagint corpus.
- Aided Search, restricted to a subset of biblical books potentially relevant to Clement of Alexandria (Genesis, Exodus, Leviticus, Numbers, Deuteronomy, Psalms, and Isaiah).

The results for the Full Search were as follows:

- Syntactic Search: 51 out of 78 references found (65.4%).
- Embedding Search: 38 out of 78 references found (48.7%).
- Hybrid Search: 55 out of 78 references found (70.5%).

The Aided Search mode yielded slightly improved results but followed the same overall trend.

Extended Evaluation of Search Configurations

To further assess and refine the retrieval system, a series of controlled experiments were conducted on the full Septuagint corpus. These tests examined the impact of different retrieval strategies and data configurations on two standard metrics: Recall@10 (R@10), which measures how often the relevant verse appears in the top 10 results, and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR), which captures how highly the correct result is ranked on average.

The following search strategies were tested:

1. **Token-Based Search:** matching based on individual word tokens (normalized forms).
2. **Fully Language-Agnostic Search:** a composite approach combining token overlap, trigrams, and word-level shingles.
3. **Semantic Search:** vector-based similarity using SPhilBERTa embeddings.

4. **Hybrid Search:** a combined scoring approach blending syntactic and semantic similarity through a linear combination.

Each configuration was executed in two modes:

- **With Apparatus:** incorporating textual variants and alternate readings from the critical apparatus of the reference edition.
- **Without Apparatus:** using only the main text established by the modern editor(s), without variant expansions.

The following table summarizes the evaluation results:

Search Type	Without Apparatus		With Apparatus	
	R@10	MRR	R@10	MRR
Token-Based	0.42	0.32	0.47	0.37
Language-Agnostic	0.40	0.32	0.56	0.42
Semantic (Embeddings)	0.33	0.26	0.33	0.21
Hybrid	0.42	0.33	0.69	0.49

Table 1. Different search strategies and their respective evaluation results.

To illustrate the performance patterns, the following plots show R@K for increasing values of K across configurations:

Figure 1. Token-based search type (with apparatus).

Figure 2. Language-agnostic search type (with apparatus).

Figure 3. Semantic (embeddings) search type (with apparatus).

Figure 4. Hybrid search type (with apparatus).

These results reveal several key insights:

- Incorporating the critical apparatus consistently improves performance across all methods.
- The semantics approach alone yields the worst performance, possibly due to lack of high-quality models for ancient languages.
- Hybrid search with apparatus achieves the best overall performance, validating the benefit of combining surface-level and semantic cues.

These findings indicate that combining syntactic and semantic methods significantly improves retrieval performance in detecting intertextual references, thereby underscoring the value of multimodal search strategies in Digital Humanities research. The Greek semantic search engine has been integrated into *uBIQUity* as a dedicated node type, enabling flexible, research-driven textual comparisons.

5.2. Latin Search Engine

To support intertextual analysis within *uBIQUity* for Latin texts, a dedicated search engine was developed with a focus on retrieving semantically related biblical passages referenced in Latin patristic literature. The primary corpus consists of two major Latin Bible versions, Jerome's *Vulgate* (W_VULG) and the *Vetus Latina* (S_VL), alongside annotated intertextual references from Augustine's *De Genesi ad litteram libri duodecim*.

The engine is built around a sentence-level semantic search model where each biblical verse is treated as a standalone retrievable unit. Unlike traditional keyword-based systems, this

search engine leverages dense vector embeddings trained to capture semantic similarity, thereby enabling the identification of allusive and stylistically varied intertextual connections.

A key innovation lies in the use of LLM-generated synthetic data to address the low-resource nature of Latin. Specifically, a state-of-the-art Latin embedding model (i.e., Latin BERT or LaBERTa in our experiments) was fine-tuned using synthetic triplets (source, positive, negative) produced by GPT-4. Positive samples retained the meaning of the source passage while varying in form, and negative samples exhibited superficial similarity but lacked true semantic correspondence. This contrastive training approach shaped a highly contextualized embedding space for Latin texts. The prompting strategy used to generate these samples is illustrated in Fig. 5.

You are given a passage from an ancient Latin Bible. Your mission is to generate a positive and a negative passage for a text retrieval task in JSON format. The JSON object must contain the following keys:

- **"positive_passage"**: a string, a positive passage that is different from the source passage but has the same meaning. It should be **longer than** the source passage.
- **"negative_passage"**: a string, a negative passage that only appears related to the source passage. It should be **of the same length as** the source passage.

Both the positive and negative passages must be in Latin. Your output must always be a JSON object only, do not explain yourself or output anything else. Be creative!

Source passage: *In principio creavit Deus caelum et terram*

```
{
  "positive_passage": "In principio omnium Deus creavit caelum et terram et omnia quae in eis sunt";
  "negative_passage": "In tempore antiquo homo exploravit caelum et mare"
}
```

Figure 5. Example of the prompt template employed for generating positive and negative samples.

Experiments were conducted on a training set comprising 35k verses from the W_VULG corpus and 23k from the S_VL corpus, including 22k overlapping passages. During training, positive pairs were formed using either GPT-4-generated positives or aligned verses from the two Bible versions. Negative samples were sourced exclusively from the LLM-generated outputs. To enhance variability, one of the two positive options was selected at random for each training instance. Representative synthetic examples are provided in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Synthetic positive and negative passages generated by GPT-4, starting from a source passage from W_VULG.

Evaluation was performed on a test set of 376 intertextual references manually annotated by the WP8 humanists from Augustine’s commentary *De Genesi ad litteram*, which are mapped to verses in both W_VULG and S_VL. Tables 2 and 3 show the retrieval results, measured in terms of the average number of queries for which the target passage is retrieved within the first k passages, with $k=\{1,2,3,5,10,20\}$ (i.e. Recall@ k). The proposed fine-tuning pipeline is compared against standard fine-tuning, where the models were trained without positive and negative passages generated by GPT-4 but only leveraging the correspondences between W_VULG and S_VL to build positive pairs for contrastive learning. Zero-shot results of the models are also provided as a reference.

Model	Pooling	Corpus: W_VULG (All)					
		R@1	R@2	R@3	R@5	R@10	R@20
Latin BERT	CLS Token	18.2	24.5	26.6	28.1	29.7	34.9
w/ standard fine-tuning		43.8	47.9	51.6	54.7	62.0	66.1
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		43.2	49.5	51.6	57.3	63.0	66.1
Latin BERT	Token Avg	33.3	38.0	41.7	44.8	47.9	50.5
w/ standard fine-tuning		44.8	51.0	54.7	58.3	64.1	68.8
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		45.8	53.1	56.3	58.9	65.6	70.3
LaBERTa	CLS Token	31.3	39.1	44.3	47.4	55.7	58.3
w/ standard fine-tuning		44.8	51.0	53.6	60.4	64.6	69.8
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		46.4	53.1	55.7	61.5	71.4	74.5
LaBERTa	Token Avg	34.4	40.6	43.8	47.9	52.6	56.8
w/ standard fine-tuning		47.4	54.2	57.3	64.6	68.2	71.4
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		47.9	54.2	57.8	66.7	75.0	77.1

Table 2. Results on the W_VULG corpus comparing the proposed fine-tuning strategy using LLM-generated synthetic data against standard fine-tuning (without generated samples) and the original (non-fine-tuned) model.

Model	Pooling	Corpus: S_VL (All)					
		R@1	R@2	R@3	R@5	R@10	R@20
Latin BERT	CLS Token	17.9	22.8	26.1	31.0	34.2	36.4
w/ standard fine-tuning		40.8	46.2	47.8	54.3	60.3	63.0
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		41.3	47.3	52.2	56.0	64.1	71.2
Latin BERT	Token Avg	37.0	41.3	44.6	48.9	53.3	55.4
w/ standard fine-tuning		40.8	46.7	51.1	56.0	63.0	67.4
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		42.9	49.5	52.7	59.2	67.9	72.3
LaBERTa	CLS Token	29.9	36.4	42.4	47.8	52.7	56.5
w/ standard fine-tuning		42.9	48.9	52.7	60.9	66.3	70.7
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		47.3	51.1	56.0	64.7	70.1	77.7
LaBERTa	Token Avg	36.4	40.2	42.4	47.3	48.4	56.0
w/ standard fine-tuning		44.0	46.7	54.9	63.0	66.8	72.3
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		48.9	52.2	56.5	63.0	71.2	78.8

Table 3. Results on the S_VL corpus comparing the proposed fine-tuning strategy using LLM-generated synthetic data against standard fine-tuning (without generated samples) and the original (non-fine-tuned) model.

Across all configurations, models fine-tuned with the synthetic data pipeline consistently outperformed those using only standard fine-tuning, with particularly strong gains observed in Recall@1. These improvements were consistent across both biblical *corpora* and embedding architectures, despite synthetic data being generated solely from the W_VULG corpus. This cross-corpus generalization underscores the robustness and transferability of the synthetic data approach for retrieval in low-resource settings.

Further validation was conducted on the most challenging subset of the test set composed of references with minimal lexical overlap (corresponding to similarity scores between 0.0 and 0.25). Results presented in Table 4 confirm that the proposed approach significantly improves retrieval effectiveness in these difficult cases. For instance, Recall@1 for Latin BERT with token averaging on W_VULG increased from 3.9% to 11.8%, representing a relative gain of over 200%. In the S_VL corpus, the same configuration achieved 8.9% Recall@1 where standard fine-tuning failed to retrieve any correct passage (0.0%). These results highlight the particular utility of synthetic data augmentation for identifying subtle, non-obvious intertextual relationships.

Model	Pooling	Corpus: W_VULG (hard)			Corpus: S_VL (hard)		
		R@1	R@5	R@10	R@1	R@5	R@10
Latin BERT	CLS Token	2.0	2.0	2.0	0.0	2.2	2.2
w/ standard fine-tuning		5.9	15.7	29.4	2.2	15.6	24.4
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		7.8	23.5	33.3	6.7	22.2	33.3
Latin BERT	Token Avg	2.0	2.0	5.9	0.0	2.2	4.4
w/ standard fine-tuning		3.9	19.6	31.4	0.0	13.3	26.7
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		11.8	25.5	37.3	8.9	26.7	37.8
LaBERTa	CLS Token	2.0	19.6	33.3	2.2	17.8	26.7
w/ standard fine-tuning		15.7	33.3	39.2	6.7	31.1	44.4
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		19.6	35.3	51.0	17.8	42.2	51.1
LaBERTa	Token Avg	0.0	5.9	9.8	2.2	2.2	2.2
w/ standard fine-tuning		17.6	37.3	45.1	8.9	35.6	44.4
w/ fine-tuning on synth. data (Ours)		19.6	39.2	54.9	15.6	33.3	46.7

Table 4. Performance comparison on the “hard” subsets of W_VULG and S_VL corpora (i.e., queries with the lowest similarity to the corresponding biblical verse).

5.3. Arabic Search Engine

For the Arabic component of the tool, which involves semantic indexing of the corpus, the WP8 team parsed the texts with an emphasis on preserving their original structure wherever possible. This included maintaining distinctions between headers, paragraphs, and verse lines, which are integral to the organization and meaning of classical Arabic texts. To prepare the texts for embedding, we implemented a chunking strategy that imposed both minimum (50) and maximum (250) length limits for string segments, balancing computational efficiency with semantic coherence. Rather than splitting arbitrarily, we aimed to preserve logical units of meaning—such as paragraph boundaries or complete verses—within each chunk. This approach ensured that the embeddings captured contextually rich and meaningful representations of the text, while respecting the stylistic and structural features of the original corpus.

To maximize the usefulness and interpretability of each embedded chunk, we augmented every chunk with comprehensive metadata drawn from the corpus and file structure. This includes attributes such as author name, work title, estimated date, source collection, and original file path. When available, we also incorporated classification information, such as literary genre or subject, derived from the OpenITI metadata files (<https://openiti.org/>). This enriched metadata enables both users and systems to filter, organize, and contextualize search results, going beyond the semantic content of the text alone.

In addition, we appended the text of the immediately preceding and following chunks to each main chunk as auxiliary fields. While these surrounding texts were not used in the semantic embedding itself, they provide browsing and interpretive context—helping users quickly understand how and where a chunk fits within the broader structure of the work.

This is particularly useful for locating passages in long or complex texts, in which a single chunk may only convey part of a larger argument or narrative.

This strategy supports both machine and human interaction: the enriched chunks are better suited for re-ranking, filtering, or display in downstream applications, while also improving the user’s ability to explore texts meaningfully in a search interface.

We also enriched each chunk by including the most relevant section header—when available—at the beginning of the text. This added contextual layer helps guide the semantic model and improves the quality of matches by providing thematic framing for the content. Finally, for semantic representation of text chunks, we adopted the omarelshehy/Arabic-Retrieval-v1.0 model, a state-of-the-art Arabic sentence transformer specifically fine-tuned for semantic textual similarity tasks (<https://huggingface.co/omarelshehy/Arabic-Retrieval-v1.0>).

Existing tools for searching across *ḥadīth* collections largely rely on Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies, but they tend to have limitations in terms of usability and accessibility. For example, Ahadith²² enables similarity-based search, allowing users to retrieve semantically related *aḥādīth*; however, the system often faces performance issues, particularly in terms of search speed. Other tools, such as Hadith-Search²³ and Hadith-Search-Engine,²⁴ are available as open-source code bases. While these can be powerful, they generally require a significant amount of technical knowledge to install, configure, and operate, which makes them less accessible to non-specialist users.

Academic institutions have also contributed to the development of *ḥadīth*-related resources. One notable example is the LK-Hadith-Corpus,²⁵ which provides a structured and annotated collection of *aḥādīth* suitable for computational analysis and research. In parallel, broader textual datasets like OpenITI²⁶ include *ḥadīth* content within larger collections of classical Arabic texts, offering researchers access to a vast linguistic and historical corpus. Platforms like the Sunnah.com²⁷ search engine have become widely used in both academic and community contexts due to their ease of access and clear presentation of canonical collections.

Despite the diversity of these tools, they all share certain key limitations. On one hand, some platforms are well-designed and user-friendly but rely on keyword-based or rigid search mechanisms, lacking the ability to interpret queries semantically. On the other hand, tools that do adopt semantic search approaches—using embeddings or similarity metrics—often face significant drawbacks in terms of usability, such as slow query times or complex user

²² <https://ahadith.app/>

²³ <https://github.com/abdukmunimjemaal/hadith-search>

²⁴ <https://github.com/mohamedkhalifa9/Hadith-Search-Engine>

²⁵ <https://github.com/ShathaTm/LK-Hadith-Corpus>

²⁶ <https://openiti.org/>

²⁷ <https://sunnah.com/>

interfaces that make them less practical for everyday users. As a result, a gap remains between the advanced technological potential and accessible, high-performance tools for *ḥadīth* exploration.

6. Methodology

All the existing digital tools presented above generate friction for several reasons: their datasets are built on limited *corpora* that do not include any critical apparatus, they are not user-friendly and fully accessible, and they do not communicate with each other due to non-interoperable outputs that hinder data sharing. The WP8-primary goal of making textual ‘filigrees’ visible—or more visible—through digital tools thus reflects an emerging need in the scientific community of Religious Studies and poses several methodological challenges. More specifically, the development of the *uBIQUity* tool is grounded in the need for new methodological paradigms capable of addressing scholarly (and non-scholarly) challenges through technologies that assimilate and extend knowledge in meaningful and expansive ways. In this context, technology must not serve as a means of simplification but rather as a vehicle for embracing the inherent complexity of ancient biblical and Islamic literatures, placing them in dialogue with a centuries-long tradition of exegetical works.

Overall, *uBIQUity* aims to fill the gaps in existing tools and improve the interpretive approach of Digital Humanities. In detecting a wide spectrum of intertextual references, the system combines ontology-based approaches with vector embeddings, integrating structured knowledge and semantic similarity. It provides researchers with a larger corpus and, thanks to a diagrammatic user interface, allows them to be active agents in the process of knowledge creation.

Beyond the theoretical and methodological aspects, **the verification and implementation of the search engine’s functionality relied on the involvement of scholars specializing in Greek, Latin, and Arabic literatures, particularly those with expertise in Religious Studies and the exegetical traditions of sacred texts. For Greek and Latin texts, we selected six academics with diverse backgrounds but a shared, deep interest in intertextuality and the reception of ancient textual and cultural traditions. Three scholars were also involved in testing the tool on Arabic texts. They came from different backgrounds but shared expertise in the intertextual dynamics typical of religious texts in the medieval Islamic tradition.**

These scholars were tasked with using the *uBIQUity* platform to conduct both WP8 team-suggested inquiries—serving as a shared testing environment—and research driven by their individual interests, free from predefined limitations. To contextualize each scholar’s background and interests, and, most importantly, to systematically

collect and analyze their feedback, a five-section questionnaire was distributed to the testers.

The form (included as an *Appendix* to this deliverable, along with the testers' responses) was designed by the WP8 team to gather both qualitative and quantitative assessments through a combination of closed and open-ended questions. Participants were first invited to describe their current practices, specifying which digital tools they routinely use for textual analysis and reuse (such as TLG, Diogenes, Tesserae, or Shamila), and to identify the key functionalities they typically seek in such instruments. They were also asked to report their level of familiarity with text reuse detection tools (e.g., TRACER), Artificial Intelligence in the humanities, and transformer-based language models like BERT.

The core of the questionnaire consisted of practical testing tasks: respondents were asked to submit specific Latin, Greek and Arabic queries—some predefined and others of their own choice—into the *uBIQUnity* prototype software and annotate the first seven or ten results returned by the engine. In addition to providing textual data, participants were asked to evaluate the relevance and quality of the results using a 4-point rating scale, and to comment on the semantic accuracy of the matches, the presence of false positives or inconsistencies, and the overall usefulness of the retrieved material.

Further questions focused on the system's ability to capture contextual meaning in Latin, Greek, and Arabic, the adequacy of surrounding textual context, and the clarity of metadata associated with each result. In the final section of the questionnaire, participants were encouraged to reflect on their overall experience, suggesting possible improvements in functionality, interface, ranking of results, and metadata presentation. They were also asked whether the tool could enrich their scholarly work, how it might be scaled to meet the needs of colleagues, and whether specific training should be offered alongside it. The form concluded with an open comment box, allowing participants to offer additional reflections, criticisms, or expressions of support for the ongoing development of the tool.

7. Findings

7.1 Greek and Latin

The overall feedback from the six expert respondents was highly positive, underscoring both the functionality and the scholarly potential of the prototype search engine, while also identifying specific areas for further refinement. Across both Latin and Greek queries—whether predefined or user-generated—participants consistently praised the tool's capacity to retrieve semantically relevant results, including non-literal textual reuses. In most cases, scholars reported that the retrieved results were meaningful within their respective fields of expertise and frequently revealed unexpected or previously unnoticed textual connections. This level of semantic sensitivity was regarded as particularly promising for advancing research on intertextuality, biblical influence, and the transmission of classical motifs.

From a technical standpoint, the search engine was generally assessed as performing well. Several reviewers explicitly described the tool as “useful and promising,” “technically sound,” and “stimulating,” particularly considering its capacity to identify connections that extend beyond surface-level textual similarity. Scholars further noted that the model demonstrates considerable potential to enrich research by accelerating discovery, promoting broader contextual thinking, and fostering new avenues of philological and historical analysis.

At the same time, participants also identified some limitations. The engine was generally considered more reliable in identifying direct quotations or close paraphrases than in capturing more subtle allusions, and some responses pointed to inconsistencies in the ranking or explanation of results. Several scholars reported difficulties in interpreting certain metadata or in understanding the rationale behind specific matches, particularly when contextual justification was not immediately evident. To address these issues, respondents suggested enhancements to the metadata structure, including the addition of biblical edition identifiers, references to the critical apparatus, and clearer contextual or chronological information about the source texts. One participant also proposed introducing customizable semantic matching parameters—such as the option to enable or disable trigram-based ranking—to allow users to fine-tune results according to their specific scholarly needs.

Several reviewers recommended that future iterations of the tool include a broader textual corpus, encompassing not only religious but also non-religious sources from antiquity and late antiquity—an observation that underscores the tool’s remarkable potential for innovation in the field of ancient studies more broadly. Ranking strategies also emerged as a recurring theme: while the relevance of the results was often acknowledged, reviewers suggested that more consistent prioritization—placing the most pertinent matches at the top—would significantly enhance usability. Despite these caveats, the clarity and navigability of the interface were widely praised.

Importantly, all respondents saw clear potential for this tool to support their research agendas, both by facilitating the detection of known parallels and by uncovering novel intertextual patterns. Most agreed that the engine could be of great interest to scholars across classical studies, theology, biblical exegesis, and the digital humanities. All six participants endorsed the idea of offering basic training or documentation, which would assist users in fully exploiting advanced features such as semantic filters and result interpretation.

Based on the responses collected through the questionnaires, the following charts and diagrams were generated to visually represent the data concerning both the academic background of the consulted experts and their evaluations of the tool’s functionalities:

What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

6 risposte

Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

6 risposte

TEAM-SUGGESTED QUERIES (LATIN)

Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

6 risposte

Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

6 risposte

TEAM-SUGGESTED QUERIES (GREEK)

Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

6 risposte

Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

6 risposte

FREE QUERIES (LATIN)

Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

5 risposte

Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

5 risposte

FREE QUERIES (GREEK)

Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

4 risposte

Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

4 risposte

RETRIEVED RESULTS AND INTERFACE

Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

6 risposte

Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

6 risposte

Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

6 risposte

Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

6 risposte

7.2. Arabic

The evaluation of the Arabic prototype tool by three domain experts yielded a range of constructive insights, revealing both the scholarly potential of the tool and several key areas requiring refinement. Despite the small size of the test group, the responses were detailed and substantive, offering diverse perspectives on the tool’s semantic capabilities, interface design, and research utility within the fields of Arabic and Islamic studies.

All three evaluators acknowledged the value of the tool’s semantic search capabilities. The tool was consistently praised for retrieving not only exact matches but also semantically relevant paraphrases and reuses. Even when no literal overlap was found, the level of semantic sensitivity of the engine often produced contextually meaningful results, offering valuable support for research in Islamic textual traditions and textual reuse across different literary genres. When testing the three preset queries, participants largely rated the results as “mostly Relevant” or “very Relevant.” However, concerns were raised regarding the clarity and completeness of metadata, including missing author information in some cases, inconsistencies in date presentation, and occasional duplication or truncation of excerpts. These issues are already being addressed through ongoing efforts to improve the metadata structure, normalize entries, and enhance bio-bibliographic accuracy across the *corpora*.

Another recurring observation concerned the ordering of results. While some testers expected canonical sources (e.g., Bukhārī, Muslim) to appear first, it is important to note that the current engine intentionally avoids privileging “canonical” over “non-canonical” texts. In future iterations, users will be able to customize ranking criteria—e.g., by semantic similarity, chronology, or source type—without predefining what constitutes “canonical.” This design choice is intended to challenge traditional biases and encourage the discovery of new textual associations. Upcoming updates will also introduce additional filtering

options, allowing users to prioritize canonical sources if desired, without enforcing such hierarchies by default.

In their custom queries, testers explored a wide range of inputs, from well-known *ʾahādīṭ* to key terms from the Islamic religious sphere, as well as bibliographic metadata. While narrative or conceptual queries produced strong results, queries such as book titles (e.g., *Rasāʾil Ibn Rushd al-Ṭibbīyyah*) or acronyms like “ISBN” in Arabic yielded few or no relevant matches. This is to be expected, as the tool is not currently designed to retrieve modern catalog metadata or structured identifiers. These results highlight the need to clarify the intended scope of the tool and the kinds of queries it is optimized to handle.

As for metadata, testers found it to be often overwhelming, unclear, incomplete, or overly technical—an issue stemming from its origins in the OpenITI corpus and other legacy data models. In response, ongoing efforts are focused on refining the metadata presentation by reducing visual clutter, standardizing field order, and distinguishing between essential bibliographic metadata and advanced technical tags. Suggestions, such as adding both Hijrī and Gregorian dates, or enabling corpus-specific filtering (e.g., Shamela), are actively being considered.

The tool’s interface was described as generally clear and usable, though still at a prototypical stage. Each participant rated the tool’s intuitiveness as a 3 out of 4. Feedback emphasized the importance of normalizing the layout of filters, improving their naming conventions, and providing structured input fields (e.g., for author, title, source). The interface presented during testing was only provisional, and it has already been completely redesigned to improve the user experience. A guided query builder and expanded search options have been introduced to better accommodate different research workflows.

The testers also indicated that training resources and documentation would be especially helpful for new users—an area we are already addressing through the development of comprehensive training materials that cover theoretical, methodological, visual, and technical dimensions. Despite its prototypical status, the tool was regarded as highly promising for advancing Arabic textual studies. All three scholars recognized its capacity to accelerate research, identify meaningful textual connections, and support broader digital humanities workflows. This evaluation thus validated both the current achievements and the roadmap for future improvements of the *uBIQUity* tool for Arabic texts.

Based on the results of the questionnaires, the following charts and diagrams have been created to visually represent the feedback received, highlighting both the backgrounds of the consulted experts and the functionalities of the tool. Meanwhile, the full responses of the three domain experts in the field of Arabic-Islamic studies are provided in the *Appendix* below.

Are you familiar with text reuse tools?

3 risposte

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please briefly describe your understanding or experience in the space below.
- Been at the Aga Khan University at the CDH centre which developed and integrated the passim algorithm into the Kitab Project corpus they have preaviously built in the OpenITI frame...

What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

3 risposte

- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

3 risposte

- Yes
- No
- If yes, please briefly describe your understanding or experience in the space below.
- Use of BERT-based models fine-tuned for arabic language such as araBERT for developing topic modeling solutions for cataloguing non-latin and Islamic studies texts

TEAM-SUGGESTED AND FREE QUERIES

We are now providing three preset queries. For each query, please: 1. Examine at least the first 10 results returned by the tool, in the order in which t... How relevant were the results returned by the tool?

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

Query 2: وكان سبب ذلك أن الجن كانت تسترق السمع فلما حرست السماء ورجموا بالشهب قال إبليس إن هذا الذي حدث في السماء لشيء حدث في الأرض (From Tafsīr al-Tha‘labī)

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

Query 3: الدجال

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your first query?

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your second query?

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your third query?

3 risposte

- 1 = Not relevant
- 2 = Slightly relevant
- 3 = Mostly relevant
- 4 = Very relevant

RETRIEVED RESULTS AND INTERFACE

How intuitive did you find the tool's interface?

3 risposte

Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

3 risposte

How well do you think the tool captures contextual meaning in Arabic?

3 risposte

Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

3 risposte

- Yes
- No
- It depends from the submitted query.
- it depends mostly on the type of query but in general the tool did a good job

Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

3 risposte

- Yes
- No
- Not always.
- Not useful except for some that should be kept (as said, those that are useful to referencing and to find the passage in the original source). The rest of the metadata follows the scheme of another project which developed their own personal metadata scheme in complia...

Would you recommend this tool to a colleague in your field?

3 risposte

Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

3 risposte

8. Conclusions

In conclusion, the feedback provided by the expert testers confirms that the *uBIQUity* prototype search engines are already functionally robust and intellectually stimulating tools, capable of supporting meaningful scholarly work. This assessment applies consistently across all three tested languages (Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic). With targeted refinements—especially in the areas of result ranking, metadata clarity, and corpus expansion—these tools, combined into a single software package/platform, are set to become valuable and widely adopted resources in the field of classical, Islamic, and early Christian textual studies.

The integration of different strategies for identifying and retrieving textual similarities—beyond the traditionally established boundaries between classical algorithms, text-reuse, and Artificial Intelligence—appears particularly promising. The feedback collected strongly supports the hypothesis that *uBIQUity* could be a true game changer, offering substantial support not only to the scholarly community engaged in Religious Studies, but also to all

those grappling with the complex challenges of intertextuality as an intrinsic feature of the textual *corpora* handed down from the past.

9. Appendix

This appendix provides a detailed account of the questions posed to the experts as well as of their responses.

9.1. *uBIQUity* - Latin and Greek Tool Test (WP8): Feedback Questionnaire

Interviewee 1

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: Diogenes, TLG, PHI Corpus, Perseus, Library of Latin Texts, MGH online, Tesserae

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: Usability and accuracy

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: I am very familiar with Diogenes, TLG, and Tesserae, which have text reuse functions. I was trained to use TRACER, but I find it too complicated

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Intermediate

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: No, I am not

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetæ labia mundavit.

A: RESULTS FOR QUERY 1:

1. corinthias-2 5:10 [weber]

omnes enim nos manifestari oportet ante tribunal Christi ut referat unusquisque propria corporis prout gessit sive bonum sive malum

Scores: 6.422, 1.000 (normalized), 10.450 (standardized)

2. corinthians-2 5:10 [sabatier-versio-antiqua]

Nam omnes vos manifestari oportet ante Tribunal Christi, ut ferat unusquisque propria corporis, secundum quod gessit; sive bonum, sive malum.

Scores: 6.358, 0.990 (normalized), 10.328 (standardized)

3. chronicles-1 28:8 [weber]

nunc igitur coram universo coetu Israhel audiente Deo nostro custodite et perquirite cuncta mandata Domini Dei nostri ut possideatis terram bonam et relinquatis eam filiis vestris post vos usque in sempiternum

Scores: 4.349, 0.674 (normalized), 6.516 (standardized)

4. Eccl 12:14 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

quia omne factum Deus adducet in iudicium de omni contemptu, sive bonum, sive malum sit.

Scores: 4.264, 0.661 (normalized), 6.355 (standardized)

5. ecclesiastes 12:14 [weber]

et cuncta quae fiunt adducet Deus in iudicium pro omni errato sive bonum sive malum sit

Scores: 4.210, 0.653 (normalized), 6.252 (standardized)

6. ezekiel 31:12 [weber]

et succident illum alieni et crudelissimi nationum et proicient eum super montes et in cunctis convallibus corruent rami eius et confringentur arbusta eius in universis rupibus terrae et recedent de umbraculo eius omnes populi terrae et relinquent eum

Scores: 4.040, 0.626 (normalized), 5.930 (standardized)

7. corinthias-2 1:6 [weber]

sive autem tribulamur pro vestra exhortatione et salute sive exhortamur pro vestra exhortatione quae operatur in tolerantia earundem passionum quas et nos patimur

Scores: 3.933, 0.609 (normalized), 5.727 (standardized)

RESULTS FOR QUERY 2:

1. esdrae-4 8:52 [weber]

Vobis enim apertus est paradisi, plantata est arbor vitae, praeparatum est futurum tempus, praeparata est abundantia, aedificata est civitas, probata est requies, perfecta est bonitas, ante perfecta sapientia.

Scores: 2.377, 1.000 (normalized), 6.587 (standardized)

2. esdrae-4-s 8:52 [weber]

Vobis enim apertus est paradisi, plantata est arbor vitae, praeparatum est futurum tempus, praeparata est abundantia, aedificata est civitas, probata est requies, perfecta est bonitas, ante perfecta sapientia.

Scores: 2.377, 1.000 (normalized), 6.587 (standardized)

3. judges 1:11 [weber]

atque inde profectus abiit ad habitatores Dabir cuius nomen vetus erat Cariathsepher id est civitas Litterarum

Scores: 2.232, 0.933 (normalized), 6.067 (standardized)

4. revelation 21:19 [weber]

fundamenta muri civitatis omni lapide pretioso ornata fundamentum primum iaspis secundus saphyrus tertius carcedonius quartus zmaragdus

Scores: 2.104, 0.875 (normalized), 5.612 (standardized)

5. Is 54:11 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Humilis, et instabilis absque consolatione. Ecce ego praepara tibi carbunculum lapidem tuum, et fundamenta tua sapphirum,

Scores: 2.092, 0.869 (normalized), 5.569 (standardized)

6. job 25:4 [weber]

numquid iustificari potest homo comparatus Deo aut apparere mundus natus de muliere

Scores: 2.085, 0.866 (normalized), 5.542 (standardized)

7. maccabees-1 6:33 [weber]

et surrexit ante lucem et concitavit exercitus impetum contra viam Bethzacara et comparaverunt se exercitus in proelium et tubis cecinerunt

Scores: 2.028, 0.840 (normalized), 5.340 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 2

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: RESULTS FOR QUERY 1:

1.daniel-theodotionis 4:35 [rahlfs]

καὶ πάντες οἱ κατοικοῦντες τὴν γῆν ὡς οὐδὲν ἐλογίσθησαν, καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ποιεῖ ἐν τῇ δυνάμει τοῦ οὐρανοῦ καὶ ἐν τῇ κατοικίᾳ τῆς γῆς, καὶ οὐκ ἔστιν ὃς ἀντιποιήσεται τῇ χειρὶ αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐρεῖ αὐτῷ Τί ἐποίησας;

Scores: 2.464, 1.000 (normalized), 6.686 (standardized)

2. sirach 32:17 [rahlfs]

ἄνθρωπος ἁμαρτωλὸς ἐκκλινεῖ ἐλεγμὸν καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ εὐρήσει σύγκριμα.

Scores: 2.252, 0.913 (normalized), 5.969 (standardized)

3.sirach 35:17 [gottingen]

ἄνθρωπος ἁμαρτωλὸς ἐκκλινεῖ ἐλεγμὸν καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ εὐρήσει σύγκριμα.

Scores: 2.252, 0.913 (normalized), 5.969 (standardized)

4.psalms 102:21 [rahlfs]

εὐλογεῖτε τὸν κύριον, πᾶσαι αἱ δυνάμεις αὐτοῦ, λειτουργοὶ αὐτοῦ ποιοῦντες τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 2.197, 0.890 (normalized), 5.784 (standardized)

5.psalms 101:21 [gottingen]

εὐλογεῖτε τὸν κύριον, πᾶσαι αἱ δυνάμεις αὐτοῦ, λειτουργοὶ αὐτοῦ ποιοῦντες τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 2.197, 0.890 (normalized), 5.784 (standardized)

6. daniel-theodotionis 11:3 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἀναστήσεται βασιλεὺς δυνατὸς καὶ κυριεύσει κυριείας πολλῆς καὶ ποιήσει κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ.

Scores: 2.171, 0.880 (normalized), 5.695 (standardized)

7.deuteronomy 15:9 [gottingen]

πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσεται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ

ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

Variants:

[R_LXX] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσεται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

[G_α] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀποστασίας τῷ λέγειν Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσεται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

RESULTS FOR QUERY 2:

1. deuteronomy 32:10 [gottingen]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

Variants:

[G_α M] ἠῦρεν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

[G_σ 344] ἠπόρησεν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

[G_α θ 344 Procop 960 Syhb] εὔρεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

[G_α M Syhb] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν κενώματι ὀλολυγμοῦ ἠφανισμένης· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

[G_σ Procop 960 Syh] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, καὶ ἐν ἀτάκτῳ καὶ ἀοικίτῳ ἠφανισμένη ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

[G_α σ θ 344] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ αὐτοῦ,

Scores: 13.248, 1.000 (normalized), 35.896 (standardized)

2. odes 2:10 [rahlfs]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν τῇ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

Scores: 10.743, 0.810 (normalized), 28.825 (standardized)

3. deuteronomy 32:10 [rahlfs]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόραν ὀφθαλμοῦ

Scores: 8.022, 0.604 (normalized), 21.140 (standardized)

4. numbers 23:14 [rahlfs]

καὶ παρέλαβεν αὐτὸν εἰς ἀγροῦ σκοπιὰν ἐπὶ κορυφὴν λελαξευμένου καὶ ὠκοδόμησεν ἐκεῖ ἑπτὰ βωμοὺς καὶ ἀνεβίβασεν μόσχον καὶ κριὸν ἐπὶ τὸν βωμόν.

Scores: 2.363, 0.175 (normalized), 5.165 (standardized)

5. numbers 23:14 [gottingen]

καὶ παρέλαβεν αὐτὸν εἰς ἀγροῦ σκοπιὰν ἐπὶ κορυφὴν λελαξευμένου, καὶ ὠκοδόμησεν ἐκεῖ ἑπτὰ βωμοὺς, καὶ ἀνεβίβασεν μόσχον καὶ κριὸν ἐπὶ τὸν βωμόν.

Scores: 2.363, 0.175 (normalized), 5.165 (standardized)

6. psalms 16:4 [rahlfs]

ἔνυξέν με ὡς κέντρον ἵππου ἐπὶ τὴν γρηγόρησιν αὐτοῦ, ὁ σωτὴρ καὶ ἀντιλήπτωρ μου ἐν παντὶ καιρῷ ἔσωσέν με.

Scores: 2.305, 0.170 (normalized), 5.002 (standardized)

7.maccabeorum-iii 12:12 [gottingen]

Ἰούδας δὲ ὑπολαβὼν ὡς ἀληθῶς ἐν πολλοῖς αὐτοὺς χρησίμους ἐπεχώρησεν εἰρήνην ἄξειν πρὸς αὐτούς· καὶ λαβόντες δεξιὰς εἰς τὰς σκηνὰς ἐχωρίσθησαν.

Scores: 2.175, 0.161 (normalized), 4.635 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: QUERY 1: Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.14.30 :ea ipsa quae in disco demonstrabantur, tamquam vera animalia

1.wisdom 19:18 [weber]

agrestia enim in aquatica convertebantur et quaecumque erant natantia in terram transiebant

Scores: 2.199, 0.971 (normalized), 4.783 (standardized)

2.Wis 19:18 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Agrestia enim in aquatica convertebantur, et quaecumque erant natantia, in terram transibant,

Scores: 2.182, 0.963 (normalized), 4.731 (standardized)

3.Ezek 1:14 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Et animalia currebant et revertebantur quasi species bezec.

Scores: 2.149, 0.948 (normalized), 4.634 (standardized)

4. romans 13:9 [sabatier-versio-antiqua]

Etenim: Non adulterabis: Non occides: Non furaberis: Non concupisces: et si quid est aliud mandatum, in hoc verbo* instauratur: Diliges proximum tuum tanquam teipsum.

Scores: 2.134, 0.941 (normalized), 4.589 (standardized)

5.esther 2:9 [weber]

quae placuit ei et invenit gratiam in conspectu illius ut adceleraret mundum muliebrem et traderet ei partes suas et septem puellas speciosissimas de domo regis et tam ipsam quam pedisequas eius ornaret atque excoleret

Scores: 2.128, 0.939 (normalized), 4.573 (standardized)

6. romans 13:9 [weber]

nam non adulterabis non occides non furaberis non concupisces et si quod est aliud mandatum in hoc verbo instauratur diliges proximum tuum tamquam te ipsum

Scores: 2.108, 0.929 (normalized), 4.512 (standardized)

7. deuteronomy 4:9 [weber]

custodi igitur temet ipsum et animam tuam sollicite ne obliviscaris verborum quae viderunt oculi tui et ne excedant de corde tuo cunctis diebus vitae tuae docebis ea filios ac nepotes tuos

Scores: 2.096, 0.924 (normalized), 4.478 (standardized)

QUERY 2: Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 4.9.16: donum Spiritus sancti, per quem diffunditur caritas in cordibus nostris.

1.romans 5:5 [weber]

spes autem non confundit quia caritas Dei diffusa est in cordibus nostris per Spiritum Sanctum qui datus est nobis

Scores: 3.355, 1.000 (normalized), 6.129 (standardized)

2.romans 5:5 [sabatier-versio-antiqua]

spes autem non confundit: quia caritas Dei diffusa est in cordibus nostris per Spiritum sanctum, qui datus est nobis.

Scores: 3.349, 0.998 (normalized), 6.115 (standardized)

3.corinthias-2 1:22 [weber]

et qui signavit nos et dedit pignus Spiritus in cordibus nostris

Scores: 3.013, 0.896 (normalized), 5.323 (standardized)

4.corinthians-2 1:22 [sabatier-versio-antiqua]

et qui signavit nos, et dedit pignus Spiritus in cordibus nostris.

Scores: 3.011, 0.896 (normalized), 5.318 (standardized)

5.timothy-2 1:14 [sabatier-versio-antiqua]

bonum depositum custodi per Spiritum sanctum, qui habitat in nobis.

Scores: 2.857, 0.849 (normalized), 4.958 (standardized)

6.timothy-2 1:14 [weber]

bonum depositum custodi per Spiritum Sanctum qui habitat in nobis

Scores: 2.851, 0.847 (normalized), 4.943 (standardized)

7.ezekiel 48:8 [weber]

et super terminum Iuda a plaga orientali usque ad plagam maris erunt primitiae quas separabitis viginti quinque milibus latitudinis et longitudinis sicuti singulae partes a plaga orientali usque ad plagam maris et erit sanctuarium in medio eius

Scores: 2.748, 0.816 (normalized), 4.700 (standardized)

QUERY 3 (SINGLE WORD): propitiatorium

1. Ex 25:20 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

extendentia alas suas, et obumbrantia super propitiatorium, et facies contra se super propitiatorium,

Scores: 1.193, 1.000 (normalized), 19.334 (standardized)

2.exodus 39:34 [weber]

velum arcam vectes propitiatorium

Scores: 1.183, 0.990 (normalized), 19.113 (standardized)

3.Num 14:20 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

... Propitius ero illis.

Scores: 1.079, 0.885 (normalized), 16.786 (standardized)

4.Psa 24:11 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Propter nomen tuum Domine et propitiaberis peccato meo, copiosum est enim.

Scores: 1.067, 0.873 (normalized), 16.518 (standardized)

5. Sir 35:3 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Et propitiationem litare sacrificii super iniustitias: et deprecatio pro peccatis, recedere ab iniustitia.

Scores: 1.062, 0.868 (normalized), 16.412 (standardized)

6.psalms 24:11 [weber]

propter nomen tuum Domine et propitiaberis peccato meo multum est enim

Scores: 1.053, 0.859 (normalized), 16.216 (standardized)

7.psalms-iuxtra-hebraicum 24:11 [weber]

propter nomen tuum propitiare iniquitati meae quoniam grandis est

Scores: 1.053, 0.859 (normalized), 16.215 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: 3.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: 3.0

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: QUERY 1. Clem. Paed. 1.5.13.2: ὁ κύριος ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ μυωπίζει τοὺς γνωρίμους, προσέχειν αὐτῷ παρορμῶν ὡς ἤδη σπεύδων πρὸς τὸν πατέρα.

1. deuteronomy 15:9 [gottingen]

πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτὸν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἔβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπίδειομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

Variants:

[R_LXX] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτὸν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἔβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπίδειομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

[G_a] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτὸν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀποστασίας τῷ λέγειν Ἐγγίζει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἔβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπίδειομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

Scores: 3.239, 0.979 (normalized), 5.115 (standardized)

2.kings-1 25:23 [rahlfs]

καὶ εἶδεν Αβιγαια τὸν Δαυὶδ καὶ ἔσπευσεν καὶ κατεπήδησεν ἀπὸ τοῦ ὄνου καὶ ἔπεσεν

ένώπιον Δαυιδ ἐπὶ πρόσωπον αὐτῆς καὶ προσεκύνησεν αὐτῷ ἐπὶ τὴν γῆν

Scores: 3.173, 0.959 (normalized), 4.973 (standardized)

3. judges-vaticanus 20:23 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἀνέβησαν οἱ υἱοὶ Ἰσραὴλ καὶ ἔκλαυσαν ἐνώπιον κυρίου ἕως ἑσπέρας καὶ ἠρώτησαν ἐν κυρίῳ λέγοντες Εἰ προσθῶμεν ἐγγίσει εἰς παράταξιν πρὸς υἱοὺς Βενιαμὴν ἀδελφοὺς ἡμῶν; καὶ εἶπεν κύριος Ἀνάβητε πρὸς αὐτούς.

Scores: 3.159, 0.955 (normalized), 4.942 (standardized)

4.kings-4 6:32 [rahlfs]

καὶ Ἐλισαῖε ἐκάθητο ἐν τῷ οἴκῳ αὐτοῦ, καὶ οἱ πρεσβύτεροι ἐκάθηον μετ' αὐτοῦ. καὶ ἀπέστειλεν ἄνδρα πρὸ προσώπου αὐτοῦ· πρὶν ἔλθειν τὸν ἄγγελον πρὸς αὐτὸν καὶ αὐτὸς εἶπεν πρὸς τοὺς πρεσβυτέρους Εἰ οἴδατε ὅτι ἀπέστειλεν ὁ υἱὸς τοῦ φονευτοῦ οὗτος ἀφελεῖν τὴν κεφαλὴν μου; ἴδετε ὡς ἂν ἔλθῃ ὁ ἄγγελος, ἀποκλείσατε τὴν θύραν καὶ παραθλίψατε αὐτὸν ἐν τῇ θύρᾳ· οὐχὶ φωνὴ τῶν ποδῶν τοῦ κυρίου αὐτοῦ κατόπισθεν αὐτοῦ;

Scores: 3.021, 0.912 (normalized), 4.646 (standardized)

5.kings-1 2:36 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἔσται ὁ περισεύων ἐν οἴκῳ σου ἡξει προσκυνεῖν αὐτῷ ὀβολοῦ ἀργυρίου λέγων Παράρρησόν με ἐπὶ μίαν τῶν ἱερατειῶν σου φαγεῖν ἄρτον. Καὶ τὸ παιδάριον Σαμουὴλ ἦν λειτουργῶν τῷ κυρίῳ ἐνώπιον Ἡλὶ τοῦ ἱερέως· καὶ ῥῆμα κυρίου ἦν τίμιον ἐν ταῖς ἡμέραις ἐκείναις, οὐκ ἦν ὄρασις διαστέλλουσα.

Scores: 2.925, 0.882 (normalized), 4.441 (standardized)

6. judges-alexandrinus 20:23 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἀνέβησαν οἱ υἱοὶ Ἰσραὴλ καὶ ἔκλαυσαν ἐνώπιον κυρίου ἕως ἑσπέρας καὶ ἐπηρώτησαν ἐν κυρίῳ λέγοντες Εἰ προσθῶ προσεγγίσει εἰς πόλεμον μετὰ Βενιαμὴν τοῦ ἀδελφοῦ μου; καὶ εἶπεν κύριος Ἀνάβητε πρὸς αὐτόν.

Scores: 2.894, 0.873 (normalized), 4.373 (standardized)

7.daniel-theodotionis 2:9 [rahlfs]

ἐὰν οὖν τὸ ἐνύπνιον μὴ ἀναγγεῖλητέ μοι, οἶδα ὅτι ῥῆμα ψευδὲς καὶ διεφθαρμένον συνέθεσθε εἰπεῖν ἐνώπιόν μου, ἕως οὗ ὁ καιρὸς παρέλθῃ· τὸ ἐνύπνιον μου εἶπατέ μοι, καὶ γνῶσομαι ὅτι τὴν σύγκρισιν αὐτοῦ ἀναγγελεῖτέ μοι.

Scores: 2.892, 0.872 (normalized), 4.369 (standardized)

QUERY 2. Clem. Paed. 1.8.62.1: καὶ ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον ἐπιστρέφει ἐπὶ καρδίαν αὐτοῦ

1.sirach 21:6 [rahlfs]

μισῶν ἐλεγμὸν ἐν ἴχνει ἁμαρτωλοῦ, καὶ ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον ἐπιστρέψει ἐν καρδίᾳ.

Scores: 3.957, 1.000 (normalized), 11.414 (standardized)

2.sirach 34:14 [rahlfs]

ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον οὐδὲν εὐλαβηθήσεται καὶ οὐ μὴ δειλιάσῃ, ὅτι αὐτὸς ἐλπὶς αὐτοῦ.

Scores: 3.304, 0.834 (normalized), 9.261 (standardized)

3.sirach 31:16 [gottingen]

ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον οὐδὲν εὐλαβηθήσεται καὶ οὐ μὴ δειλιάσῃ, ὅτι αὐτὸς ἐλπὶς αὐτοῦ.

Scores: 3.298, 0.832 (normalized), 9.240 (standardized)

4.sirach 21:6 [gottingen]

μισῶν ἐλεγμὸν ἐν ἴχνει ἁμαρτωλοῦ, καὶ ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον ἐπιστρέψει ἐν καρδίᾳ.

Scores: 3.133, 0.790 (normalized), 8.696 (standardized)

5.sirach 15:1 [rahlfs]

Ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον ποιήσει αὐτό, καὶ ὁ ἐγκρατὴς τοῦ νόμου καταλήμψεται αὐτήν.

Scores: 3.019, 0.761 (normalized), 8.320 (standardized)

6.sirach 15:1 [gottingen]

Ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον ποιήσει αὐτό, καὶ ὁ ἐγκρατὴς τοῦ νόμου καταλήμψεται αὐτήν.

Scores: 3.019, 0.761 (normalized), 8.320 (standardized)

7.sirach 6:17 [rahlfs]

ὁ φοβούμενος κύριον εὐθυνεῖ φιλίαν αὐτοῦ, ὅτι κατ' αὐτὸν οὕτως καὶ ὁ πλησίον αὐτοῦ.

Scores: 2.944, 0.742 (normalized), 8.071 (standardized)

QUERY 3 (SINGLE WORD): βδέλυγμα

1. proverbs 15:26 [rahlfs]

βδέλυγμα κυρίῳ λογισμὸς ἄδικος, ἀγνῶν δὲ ῥήσεις σεμναί.

Scores: 1.650, 1.000 (normalized), 13.416 (standardized)

2. proverbs 27:20a [rahlfs]

βδέλυγμα κυρίῳ στηρίζων ὀφθαλμόν, καὶ οἱ ἀπαίδευτοι ἀκρατεῖς γλώσση.

Scores: 1.631, 0.986 (normalized), 13.190 (standardized)

3. sirach 15:13 [gottingen]

πᾶν βδέλυγμα ἐμίσησεν κύριος, καὶ οὐκ ἔστιν ἀγαπητὸν τοῖς φοβουμένοις αὐτόν.

Scores: 1.587, 0.956 (normalized), 12.688 (standardized)

4. sirach 15:13 [rahlfs]

πᾶν βδέλυγμα ἐμίσησεν ὁ κύριος, καὶ οὐκ ἔστιν ἀγαπητὸν τοῖς φοβουμένοις αὐτόν.

Scores: 1.569, 0.943 (normalized), 12.478 (standardized)

5. genesis 4:10 [gottingen]

καὶ εἶπεν ὁ θεός Τί ἐποίησας; φωνὴ αἵματος τοῦ ἀδελφοῦ σου βοᾷ πρὸς με ἐκ τῆς γῆς.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶπεν ὁ θεός Τί ἐποίησας; φωνὴ αἵματος τοῦ ἀδελφοῦ σου βοᾷ πρὸς με ἐκ τῆς γῆς.

Scores: 1.086, 0.604 (normalized), 6.934 (standardized)

6.sirach 13:20 [rahlfs]

βδέλυγμα ὑπερηφάνῳ ταπεινότης· οὕτως βδέλυγμα πλουσίῳ πτωχός.

Scores: 1.061, 0.587 (normalized), 6.655 (standardized)

7.sirach 13:20 [göttingen]

βδέλυγμα ὑπερηφάνῳ ταπεινότης· οὕτως βδέλυγμα πλουσίῳ πτωχός.

Scores: 1.061, 0.587 (normalized), 6.655 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: 4.0

**Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches?
Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?**

A: Yes

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: Yes

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: Allusions seem to be more hard to capture than literal or quasi-literal quotations .
Moreover, in one case, even if my query included an explicit reference to the Gospel (ἐν τῷ εὐαγγελίῳ), the search engine's results referred to the Old Testament.

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: Pretty well

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: Yes

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: I must confess I had difficulties in understanding the meaning of metadata

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: No

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: The tool is very useful and promising. It just needs to be improved and refined

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: I am not a fan of metadata

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: This model can provide significant textual parallels, creating unexpected connections between famous and less famous texts on the basis of their semantic relationships.

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: Clear instructions should be given in order to allow users to adjust research criteria (text, semantic et sim.) to their specific needs. For instance, in some cases semantic connections can be far more important than trigrams - and users should be instructed to disable the latter criterion.

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: The scope of the model should be extended by uploading additional texts - ultimately including non-religious sources.

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: Yes

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: Fingers crossed for the next steps of this ambitious work!

Interviewee 2

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: TLG, TLL, Bibleworks, DBG

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: Searching for single lemmas or phrases; parallel analysis of Hebrew, Greek and Latin texts of the Bible(s); searching for words or expressions in large *corpora* (Greek and Latin literature; LXX; Latin Bibles); analysis of textual recurrences; study of rewritings and ways of repropounding biblical texts in subsequent ancient literature

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: Scarcely familiar

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Beginner

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: Scarcely familiar

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetiae labia mundavit.

A: The first search has an effectiveness of 60% compared to the reference texts identified. The search tool identifies a series of textual links to biblical texts that revolve around the relationship between people and judgment, with the identification, in 6 out of 10 cases, of particularly relevant passages. The second search proved completely inadequate. I believe that the use of the term *carbo* misled the tool, which linked it to names of precious stones or, more generally, to natural elements. I did not find any relevant references in the first 10 positions.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 1

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: The first search showed remarkable effectiveness in 5 out of 10 cases, all revolving around the term thelema. The other references identified are quite relevant. The second search proved very effective in 3 out of 10 cases, as it is an almost literal quotation from Deut 32:10. The other references identified do not appear to be relevant.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 2

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: Gen. Litt. 1.5.10 Non enim habet informem vitam Verbum Filius, cui non solum hoc est esse quod vivere, sed etiam hoc est vivere, quod est sapienter ac beate vivere.

Gen. Litt. 1.8.14 Ita etiam rebus ex illa inchoatione perfectis atque formatis, vidit Deus quia bonum est

inchoatione

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: 1.0

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: Paed. 1.1 Κεκρότηται κρηπις ἀληθείας, ὃ παῖδες ὑμεῖς, ἡμῖν αὐτοῖς, ἀγίου νεῶ μεγάλου θεοῦ θεμέλιος γνώσεως ἀρραγής, προτροπή

Paed. 1.3 ἄριστον μὲν οὖν τὸ μηδ ὄλως ἐξαμαρτάνειν κατὰ μηδένα τρόπον, ὃ δὴ φαμεν εἶναι θεοῦ

ἀκηλίδωτος

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches? Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?

A: Yes

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: In some cases, very relevant. in other cases, no

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: In some cases, the references found are based on associations that are not particularly relevant (natural or collective names, apparently synonymous terms). In other cases, however, the references are relevant (especially when the text explicitly quotes or

indirectly refers to a biblical text in a fairly obvious way). The tool is most effective when a phrase that is not too long is entered in the search string.

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: In some cases very much, in others less so

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: Yes

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: Yes

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: No

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: See above

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: No

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: It implements this to the extent that it is able to find textual associations not reported in the tradition of studies of a particular text or when it is able to identify reference texts based on relevant synonymic associations or textual variants of the biblical text overlooked by modern and contemporary commentators.

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: Technically, it works very well

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: We should find a way, if possible, to organize the search results differently, indicating the degrees of greater or lesser relevance, or finding a different order (from most relevant to least relevant).

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: Yes

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: nan

Interviewee 3

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: TLG, Die Bibel-Deutsche Bibel Gesellschaft, Sefaria (Hebrew), TLL

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: Typically, I look for single lemmas or group of words (text analysis) or I look for the recurrence of biblical themes, terminology, and verses in the works of Christian authors

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: Scarsely familiar with TRACER and similar tools

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Beginner

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: Not too much

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetiae labia mundavit.

A: The first query produced intriguing results, but the second seems to have returned inaccurate data.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 1

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: The first query is somewhat interesting, though it appears to focus exclusively on the word θέλημα. The second query at a first sight seems more compelling, especially given the verbatim matches among the top three results; however, the relevance seems to diminish beyond that point.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 2

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: My first query was from "De Genesi ad litteram" I. 1.1 (Omnis divina Scriptura bipartita est, secundum id quod Dominus significat, dicens, scribam eruditum in regno Dei similem esse patrifamilias proferenti de thesauro suo nova et vetera, quae duo etiam Testamenta dicuntur). Only the first and second results are relevant. The second query was from "De Genesi ad litteram" I.1.3 (An coelum intellegendum est creatura spiritalis, ab exordio quo facta est) and, again, only the first two results seem (strongly) relevant. The third query (word "creatura") proved to be extremely relevant, with very interesting results.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: 1.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: 4.0

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: The first query is from Clem., Paed. I,5,22: Ἐγέλα δὲ κάκεϊνος τοῦ θανάτου λελυμένος. Many out of ten results are just irrelevant, but three out ten prove to be highly relevant (Gen 22) and they are in second, sixth and seventh position. The second query is from Clem., Paed. I,5,21 : Ἐγὼ καὶ τὸν Ἰσαὰκ εἰς παῖδα ἀναφέρω· γέλωσ ἐρμηνεύεται ὁ Ἰσαάκ. In this case the first seven results are definitely relevant. When searching for a specific word, the query yields moderately relevant results.

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches? Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?

A: Generally speaking, yes.

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: The results were quite meaningful, especially when they are correct.

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: Yes, I noticed errors or inconsistencies. In some cases they seem to have been triggered by single words or ideas present in the text. In other cases it seems simply impossible to understand why the tool presented certain results.

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: Medium.

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: Definitely yes.

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: Defintely yes.

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: No.

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: The general impression is good. The tool is definitely very stimulating, although one might wish that the most relevant results appeared all at once right from the start.

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: The metadata are absolutely sufficient.

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: It can certainly make the work easier and faster, while also more challenging - provided it offers more material to engage with thoughtfully.

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: The tool is working well overall. It would be even better if there were fewer irrelevant results among the relevant ones.

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: See above. The only improvement needed would be in the ranking of the relevant results.

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: Yes, I think so.

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: nan

Interviewee 4

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: Diogenes; Phi corpus; TLG

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: allusivity; quotationa

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: No

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Intermediate

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: No

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetiae labia mundavit.

A: Query 1. Eccl 12:14; Tob 14:6; Tob 3:16; 2Mac 3:6; Lev 12:2; 1Mac 1:57; Psa 21:27

Query 2: esdrae-4 8:52; judges 1:11; revelation 21:19; Is 54:11; job 25:4; maccabees-1 6:33; 1Mac 2:23

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 3

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: Query 1: daniel-theodotionis 4:35; sirach 35:17; sirach 32:17; psalms 101:21; deuteronomy 15:9; daniel-theodotionis 11:3; esdras-a 9:9 Query 2: deuteronomy 32:10; odes 2:10; deuteronomy 32:10; numbers 23:14; numbers 23:14; psalms 16:4; maccabeorum-iii 12:12

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: Query 1: Laudate Dominum de terra, dracones et omnes abyssi Psa 148:7; psalms-iuxtra-hebraicum 148:7; Psa 148:1; psalms-iuxtra-hebraicum 148:1; psalms-iuxtra-hebraicum 116:1; daniel 3:60; jeremiah 51:48 Query 2: alias capite albo sicut lana, alias inferiore parte corporis sicut aurichalcum: song-of-solomon 7:5; chronicles-2 21:19; Esth 2:7; Sir 34:6; ephesians 6:5; esdrae-2 9:24; leviticus 13:10 Query 3: multiplicamini: Gen 9:7; genesis 1:22; leviticus 26:9; isaiah 8:9; zachariah 10:8; psalms 138:18; Lev 26:9

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: 3.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: 4.0

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: nan

Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches? Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?

A: Yes, not always in the same way

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: Yes

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: Some passages have only a vague resemblance to the biblical source

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: Sufficiently well

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: yes

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: yes, the indication of the specific biblical version is useful, but other metadata should be added

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: No

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: The tool is useful and sufficiently balanced, but needs to be improved in order to capture further allusive reuses

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: The date and place of origin of all sources could be indicated

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: The model could support the investigation of quotations and allusions in a wide range of late antique texts

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: More information should be provided regarding the context and the origin of each source

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: Other texts of different kinds could be included among the sources available on the tool

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: Yes

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: Nothing to add

Interviewee 5

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: TLG, PHI Corpus, Corpus Corporum

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: Advanced research also with co-occurrence

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: No, I am not

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Beginner

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: No

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetiae labia mundavit.

A: Query 1: corinthias-2 5:10 [weber]; corinthians-2 5:10 [sabatier-versio-antiqua], chronicles-1 28:8 [weber], Eccl 12:14 [sabatier-vetus-latina], ecclesiastes 12:14 [weber], ezeziel 31:12 [weber], corinthias-2 1:6 [weber]

Query 2: judges 1:11 [weber]; revelation 21:19 [weber]; Is 54:11 [sabatier-vetus-latina]; job 25:4 [weber]; maccabees-1 6:33 [weber]; judges 1:11 [weber], esdrae-4 8:52 [weber], esdrae-4-s 8:52 [weber]

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 2

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: Query 1: daniel-theodotionis 4:35 [rahlfs]; sirach 35:17 [gottingen], psalms 102:21 [rahlfs], psalms 101:21 [gottingen], daniel-theodotionis 11:3 [rahlfs], deuteronomy 15:9 [gottingen]

Query 2: deuteronomy 32:10 [gottingen], odes 2:10 [rahlfs], deuteronomy 32:10 [rahlfs], numbers 23:14 [rahlfs], numbers 23:14 [gottingen], psalms 16:4 [rahlfs], maccabeorum-iii 12:12 [gottingen]

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: Query 1 (Aug. De anima et eius orig. 1.4.4): in hominis faciem sufflavit, eique illo modo animam fecit;

Results: Gen 2:7 [sabatier-vetus-latina]; Judith 2:7 [sabatier-vetus-latina]; genesis 2:7 [weber], isaiah 9:7 [weber], matthew 26:29 [weber], genesis 19:28 [weber], Tob 5:2 [sabatier-vetus-latina]

Query 2 (Aug. De anima et eius orig. 1.8.9): alioquin gratia iam non est gratia

Results: romans 11:6 [weber]; romans 11:6 [sabatier-versio-antiqua], ephesians 2:8 [weber], ephesians 2:8 [sabatier-versio-antiqua], galatians 2:21 [weber], galatians 2:21 [sabatier-versio-antiqua], romans 4:4 [weber]

Query 3: perfusum

Results: leviticus 8:30 [weber], ezeziel 24:7 [weber], Ex 4:9 [sabatier-vetus-latina], revelation 16:4 [weber], leviticus 8:12 [weber], 1Mac 1:39 [sabatier-vetus-latina], hosea 10:7 [weber]

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: 4.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: 4.0

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: nan

Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches? Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?

A: Yes, with the exception of one allusive reference

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: Yes

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: The tool is sometimes less efficient in detecting allusive re-uses

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: Pretty well

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: Yes, but it would be useful if one could switch to the full context of each quotation

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: The reference to the biblical version is useful. Instead, the metadata following each result are a bit obscure to me

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: Not really

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: It is a useful tool, especially in order to retrieve non-literal quotations, allusions, and paraphrases

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: One could mention the volume and the publication date of each edition of biblical books

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: By offering parallels and materials for text analysis

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: Other metadata could be added; the critical apparatus could be added for all texts

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: See above

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: Yes, of course

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: Nothing

Interviewee 6

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Greek and Latin sources you work on?

A: TLG, BiblIndex

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A: Reliable platforms for speed, clarity, and ease of consultation. I prefer those with up-to-date and comprehensive source codes.

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools (such as TRACER)?

A: No, I recently started using Tracer (a year ago).

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A: Intermediate

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A: No

Q: LATIN. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 7.25: ratio reddenda est in iudicio Dei, recepturo unoquoque secundum ea, quae per corpus gessit, sive bonum sive malum.

Query 2. Aug. De Gen. ad litt. 12.2.5: ara, unde carbo assumptus Prophetiae labia mundavit.

A: Query 1:

2Cor 5:21 [nestle-aland-28]

τὸν μὴ γνόντα ἁμαρτίαν ὑπὲρ ἡμῶν ἁμαρτίαν ἐποίησεν, ἵνα ἡμεῖς γενώμεθα δικαιοσύνη θεοῦ ἐν αὐτῷ.

Scores: 0.806, 1.000 (normalized), 1.054 (standardized)

Rom 5:18 [nestle-aland-28]

Ἄρα οὖν ὡς δι' ἐνὸς παραπτώματος εἰς πάντας ἀνθρώπους εἰς κατάκριμα, οὕτως καὶ δι' ἐνὸς δικαίωματος εἰς πάντας ἀνθρώπους εἰς δικαίωσιν ζωῆς·

Scores: 0.803, 0.992 (normalized), 1.038 (standardized)

sirach 16:12 [göttingen]

κατὰ τὸ πολὺ ἔλεος αὐτοῦ, οὕτως καὶ ὁ ἔλεγχος αὐτοῦ· ἄνδρα κατὰ τὰ ἔργα αὐτοῦ κρινεῖ.

Scores: 0.796, 0.977 (normalized), 1.006 (standardized)

James 2:13 [nestle-aland-28]

ἡ γὰρ κρίσις ἀνέλεος τῶ μὴ ποιήσαντι ἔλεος· κατακαυχᾶται ἔλεος κρίσεως.

Scores: 0.794, 0.973 (normalized), 0.997 (standardized)

Heb 5:1 [nestle-aland-28]

Πᾶς γὰρ ἀρχιερεὺς ἐξ ἀνθρώπων λαμβανόμενος ὑπὲρ ἀνθρώπων καθίσταται τὰ πρὸς τὸν θεόν, ἵνα προσφέρῃ δῶρά τε καὶ θυσίας ὑπὲρ ἁμαρτιῶν,

Scores: 0.793, 0.970 (normalized), 0.991 (standardized)

1John 3:9 [nestle-aland-28]

Πᾶς ὁ γεγεννημένος ἐκ τοῦ θεοῦ ἁμαρτίαν οὐ ποιεῖ, ὅτι σπέρμα αὐτοῦ ἐν αὐτῷ μένει, καὶ οὐ δύναται ἁμαρτάνειν, ὅτι ἐκ τοῦ θεοῦ γεγέννηται.

Scores: 0.792, 0.968 (normalized), 0.988 (standardized)

sirach 32:17 [rahlfs]

ἄνθρωπος ἁμαρτωλὸς ἐκκλινεῖ ἐλεγμὸν καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ εὐρήσει σύγκριμα.

Scores: 0.792, 0.968 (normalized), 0.987 (standardized)

Query 2:

kings-3 13:5 [rahlfs]

καὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον ἐρράγη, καὶ ἐξεχύθη ἡ πιότης ἀπὸ τοῦ θυσιαστηρίου κατὰ τὸ τέρας, ὃ ἔδωκεν ὁ ἄνθρωπος τοῦ θεοῦ ἐν λόγῳ κυρίου.

Scores: 0.799, 1.000 (normalized), 1.038 (standardized)

leviticus 8:11 [gottingen]

καὶ ἔρρανεν ἀπ' αὐτοῦ ἐπὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον ἐπτάκις, καὶ ἔχρισεν τὸ θυσιαστήριον καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτό, καὶ πάντα τὰ σκεύη αὐτοῦ καὶ τὸν λουτήρα καὶ τὴν βάσιν αὐτοῦ, καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτά· καὶ ἔχρισεν τὴν σκηνὴν καὶ πάντα τὰ ἐν αὐτῇ, καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτήν.

Scores: 0.796, 0.993 (normalized), 1.024 (standardized)

leviticus 9:20 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἐπέθηκεν τὰ στέατα ἐπὶ τὰ στηθῦνια, καὶ ἀνήνεγκαν τὰ στέατα ἐπὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον.

Scores: 0.796, 0.992 (normalized), 1.022 (standardized)

leviticus 9:20 [gottingen]

καὶ ἐπέθηκεν τὰ στέατα ἐπὶ τὰ στηθῦνια, καὶ ἀνήνεγκαν τὰ στέατα ἐπὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον·

Scores: 0.795, 0.991 (normalized), 1.020 (standardized)

leviticus 8:11 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἔρρανεν ἀπ' αὐτοῦ ἐπὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον ἐπτάκις καὶ ἔχρισεν τὸ θυσιαστήριον καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτὸ καὶ πάντα τὰ σκεύη αὐτοῦ καὶ τὸν λουτήρα καὶ τὴν βάσιν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτά· καὶ ἔχρισεν τὴν σκηνὴν καὶ πάντα τὰ ἐν αὐτῇ καὶ ἡγίασεν αὐτήν.

Scores: 0.793, 0.986 (normalized), 1.009 (standardized)

chronicles-2 1:5 [rahlfs]

καὶ τὸ θυσιαστήριον τὸ χαλκοῦν, ὃ ἐποίησεν Βεσελεηλ υἱὸς Ουριου υἱοῦ Ὡρ, ἐκεῖ ἦν ἔναντι τῆς σκηνῆς κυρίου, καὶ ἐξεζήτησεν αὐτὸ Σαλωμων καὶ ἡ ἐκκλησία,

Scores: 0.791, 0.980 (normalized), 0.998 (standardized)

exodus 40:25 [gottingen]

καὶ ἐθυμίασεν ἐπ' αὐτοῦ τὸ θυμίαμα τῆς συνθέσεως, καθάπερ συνέταξεν κύριος τῷ Μουσή.

Scores: 0.789, 0.976 (normalized), 0.988 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (LATIN)

A: 3

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (LATIN)

A: 3

Q: GREEK. Please perform the two queries suggested below. Please annotate here the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

Query 1. Clem. Paed. 1.6.27: ὡς τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ ἔργον ἐστὶ καὶ τοῦτο κόσμος ὀνομάζεται

Query 2. Clem. Paed. 1.7.56: ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

A: query 1:

sirach 35:17 [gottingen]

ἄνθρωπος ἁμαρτωλὸς ἐκκλινεῖ ἐλεγμὸν καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ εὐρήσει σύγκριμα.

Scores: 2.252, 1.000 (normalized), 5.963 (standardized)

sirach 32:17 [rahlfs]

ἄνθρωπος ἁμαρτωλὸς ἐκκλινεῖ ἐλεγμὸν καὶ κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ εὐρήσει σύγκριμα.

Scores: 2.252, 1.000 (normalized), 5.963 (standardized)

psalms 101:21 [gottingen]

εὐλογεῖτε τὸν κύριον, πᾶσαι αἱ δυνάμεις αὐτοῦ, λειτουργοὶ αὐτοῦ ποιοῦντες τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 2.197, 0.975 (normalized), 5.778 (standardized)

psalms 102:21 [rahlfs]

εὐλογεῖτε τὸν κύριον, πᾶσαι αἱ δυνάμεις αὐτοῦ, λειτουργοὶ αὐτοῦ ποιοῦντες τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 2.197, 0.975 (normalized), 5.778 (standardized)

deuteronomy 15:9 [göttingen]

πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίξει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

Variants:

[R_LXX] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀνόμημα, λέγων Ἐγγίξει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

[G_a] πρόσεχε σεαυτῷ, μὴ γένηται ῥῆμα κρυπτόν ἐν τῇ καρδίᾳ σου, ἀποστασίας τῷ λέγειν Ἐγγίξει τὸ ἔτος τὸ ἕβδομον, ἔτος τῆς ἀφέσεως, καὶ πονηρεύσῃται ὁ ὀφθαλμὸς σου τῷ ἀδελφῷ σου τῷ ἐπιδομένῳ, καὶ οὐ δώσεις αὐτῷ, καὶ βοήσεται κατὰ σοῦ πρὸς κύριον, καὶ ἔσται ἐν σοὶ ἁμαρτία μεγάλη.

Scores: 2.174, 0.965 (normalized), 5.698 (standardized)

daniel-theodotionis 11:3 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἀναστήσεται βασιλεὺς δυνατὸς καὶ κυριεύσει κυριείας πολλῆς καὶ ποιήσει κατὰ τὸ θέλημα αὐτοῦ.

Scores: 2.171, 0.964 (normalized), 5.690 (standardized)

psalms 89:17 [rahlfs]

καὶ ἔστω ἡ λαμπρότης κυρίου τοῦ θεοῦ ἡμῶν ἐφ' ἡμᾶς, καὶ τὰ ἔργα τῶν χειρῶν ἡμῶν κατεύθυνον ἐφ' ἡμᾶς.

Scores: 2.166, 0.961 (normalized), 5.671 (standardized)

Query 2:

deuteronomy 32:10 [göttingen]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνύδρῳ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,

Variants:

[G_α M] ἤρην ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,
[G_σ 344] ἠπόρησεν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,
[G_α θ 344 Procop 960 Syhb] εὔρην αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,
[G_α M Syhb] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν κενώματι ὀλολυγμοῦ ἠφανισμένης· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,
[G_σ Procop 960 Syh] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, καὶ ἐν ἀτάκτῳ καὶ ἀοικήτῳ ἠφανισμένη ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ,
[G_α σ θ 344] αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ αὐτοῦ,

Scores: 13.253, 1.000 (normalized), 35.976 (standardized)

odes 2:10 [rahlfs]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν τῇ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόρην ὀφθαλμοῦ

Scores: 10.753, 0.811 (normalized), 28.905 (standardized)

deuteronomy 32:10 [rahlfs]

αὐτάρκησεν αὐτὸν ἐν γῆ ἐρήμῳ, ἐν δίψει καύματος ἐν ἀνδρῷ· ἐκύκλωσεν αὐτὸν καὶ ἐπαίδευσεν αὐτὸν καὶ διεφύλαξεν αὐτὸν ὡς κόραν ὀφθαλμοῦ

Scores: 8.023, 0.604 (normalized), 21.184 (standardized)

numbers 23:14 [göttingen]

καὶ παρέλαβεν αὐτὸν εἰς ἀγροῦ σκοπιὰν ἐπὶ κορυφὴν λελαξευμένου, καὶ ὠκοδόμησεν ἐκεῖ ἑπτὰ βωμούς, καὶ ἀνεβίβασεν μόσχον καὶ κριὸν ἐπὶ τὸν βωμόν.

Scores: 2.358, 0.174 (normalized), 5.161 (standardized)

numbers 23:14 [rahlfs]

καὶ παρέλαβεν αὐτὸν εἰς ἀγροῦ σκοπιὰν ἐπὶ κορυφὴν λελαξευμένου καὶ ὠκοδόμησεν ἐκεῖ ἑπτὰ βωμούς καὶ ἀνεβίβασεν μόσχον καὶ κριὸν ἐπὶ τὸν βωμόν.

Scores: 2.358, 0.174 (normalized), 5.161 (standardized)

psalms 16:4 [rahlfs]

ἔνυξέν με ὡς κέντρον ἵππου ἐπὶ τὴν γρηγόρησιν αὐτοῦ, ὁ σωτὴρ καὶ ἀντιλήπτωρ μου ἐν παντὶ καιρῷ ἔσωσέν με.

Scores: 2.300, 0.170 (normalized), 4.996 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 1 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of Query 2 (GREEK)

A: 4

Q: LATIN. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A:

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query

A: nan

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query

A: nan

Q: GREEK. Please perform two queries of your own choice and then search for one specific word. Please annotate here your queries together with the first seven results returned by the model for each query:

A: Query 1: Nonnus Panopolitanus, Paraphrasis sancti evangelii Joannei, IX 12-14: οὗτος ἀλιτραίνων θεὸν ἤκαχεν ἢ ἐ τοκῆες, εἰσόκε μιν δασπληῆτες ἐμαιώσαντο λοχεῖαι μητέρος ἐκ λαγόνων ἀλαώπιδι σύγχρονον ὄρφνη

Results:

11698 Results in 139 ms

song-of-solomon 1:10 [rahlfs]

τί ὠραιώθησαν σιαγόνες σου ὡς τρυγόνες, τράχηλός σου ὡς ὀρμίσκοι;

Scores: 1.288, 1.000 (normalized), 17.574 (standardized)

genesis 48:22 [gottingen]

ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι Σίκιμα ἐξάριετον ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἣν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

Variants:

[G_α] ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι ὦμον ἕνα ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἣν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς

Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

[G_σ Ish] ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι ὄμον ἕνα ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἦν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς

Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

Scores: 1.071, 0.804 (normalized), 13.318 (standardized)

genesis 18:6 [göttingen]

καὶ ἔσπευσεν Ἀβραὰμ ἐπὶ τὴν σκηνὴν πρὸς Σάρραν καὶ εἶπεν αὐτῇ Σπεῦσον καὶ φύρασον
τρία μέτρα σεμιδάλεως καὶ ποιήσον ἐγκρυφίας.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ ἔσπευσεν Ἀβρααμ ἐπὶ τὴν σκηνὴν πρὸς Σαρραν καὶ εἶπεν αὐτῇ Σπεῦσον καὶ
φύρασον τρία μέτρα σεμιδάλεως καὶ ποιήσον ἐγκρυφίας.

Scores: 0.921, 0.668 (normalized), 10.372 (standardized)

genesis 49:11 [göttingen]

δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῇ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ
ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·

Variants:

[R_LXX] δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῇ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου
αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·

[R_LXX] δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῇ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου
αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 0.896, 0.645 (normalized), 9.883 (standardized)

exodus 3:17 [göttingen]

καὶ εἶπα Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν Χανααίων
καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Ἰεβουσαίων,
εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶπον Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν
Χανααίων καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ
Ἰεβουσαίων, εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶπον Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν
Χανααίων καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ
Ἰεβουσαίων, εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

Scores: 0.869, 0.621 (normalized), 9.366 (standardized)

genesis 3:6 [göttingen]

καὶ εἶδεν ἡ γυνὴ ὅτι καλὸν τὸ ξύλον εἰς βρῶσιν, καὶ ὅτι ἀρεστὸν τοῖς ὀφθαλμοῖς ἰδεῖν καὶ
ὥραϊόν ἐστιν τοῦ κατανοῆσαι, καὶ λαβοῦσα τοῦ καρποῦ αὐτοῦ ἔφαγεν· καὶ ἔδωκεν καὶ τῷ
ἀνδρὶ αὐτῆς μετ' αὐτῆς, καὶ ἔφαγον.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶδεν ἡ γυνὴ ὅτι καλὸν τὸ ξύλον εἰς βρῶσιν καὶ ὅτι ἀρεστὸν τοῖς ὀφθαλμοῖς

ιδεῖν καὶ ὠραῖόν ἐστιν τοῦ κατανοῆσαι, καὶ λαβοῦσα τοῦ καρποῦ αὐτοῦ ἔφαγεν· καὶ ἔδωκεν καὶ τῷ ἀνδρὶ αὐτῆς μετ’ αὐτῆς, καὶ ἔφαγον.

Scores: 0.852, 0.606 (normalized), 9.030 (standardized)

proverbs 26:26 [rahlfs]

εδρῖοις.

Scores: 0.818, 0.575 (normalized), 8.369 (standardized)

Query 2_word: ἀλιτραίνων

song-of-solomon 1:10 [rahlfs]

τί ὠραιώθησαν σιαγόνες σου ὡς τρυγόνες, τράχηλός σου ὡς ὀρμίσκοι;

Scores: 1.288, 1.000 (normalized), 17.574 (standardized)

genesis 48:22 [gottingen]

ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι Σίκιμα ἐξαίρετον ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἣν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

Variants:

[G_α] ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι ὄμμον ἕνα ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἣν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

[G_σ Ish] ἐγὼ δὲ δίδωμί σοι ὄμμον ἕνα ὑπὲρ τοὺς ἀδελφούς σου, ἣν ἔλαβον ἐκ χειρὸς Ἀμορραίων ἐν μαχαίρα μου καὶ τόξῳ.

Scores: 1.071, 0.804 (normalized), 13.318 (standardized)

genesis 18:6 [gottingen]

καὶ ἔσπευσεν Ἀβραὰμ ἐπὶ τὴν σκηνὴν πρὸς Σάρραν καὶ εἶπεν αὐτῇ Σπεῦσον καὶ φύρασον τρία μέτρα σεμιδάλεως καὶ ποιήσον ἐγκρυφίας.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ ἔσπευσεν Ἀβρααμ ἐπὶ τὴν σκηνὴν πρὸς Σαρραν καὶ εἶπεν αὐτῇ Σπεῦσον καὶ φύρασον τρία μέτρα σεμιδάλεως καὶ ποιήσον ἐγκρυφίας.

Scores: 0.921, 0.668 (normalized), 10.372 (standardized)

genesis 49:11 [gottingen]

δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῇ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·

Variants:

[R_LXX] δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῇ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου

αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·
[R_LXX] δεσμεύων πρὸς ἄμπελον τὸν πῶλον αὐτοῦ καὶ τῆ ἔλικι τὸν πῶλον τῆς ὄνου
αὐτοῦ· πλυνεῖ ἐν οἴνῳ τὴν στολὴν αὐτοῦ καὶ ἐν αἵματι σταφυλῆς τὴν περιβολὴν αὐτοῦ·

Scores: 0.896, 0.645 (normalized), 9.883 (standardized)
exodus 3:17 [gottingen]

καὶ εἶπα Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν Χανααναίων
καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Ἰεβουσαίων,
εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶπον Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν
Χανααναίων καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ
Ἰεβουσαίων, εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶπον Ἀναβιβάσω ὑμᾶς ἐκ τῆς κακώσεως τῶν Αἰγυπτίων εἰς τὴν γῆν τῶν
Χανααναίων καὶ Χετταίων καὶ Ἀμορραίων καὶ Φερεζαίων καὶ Γεργεσαίων καὶ Εὐαίων καὶ
Ἰεβουσαίων, εἰς γῆν ῥέουσαν γάλα καὶ μέλι.

Scores: 0.869, 0.621 (normalized), 9.366 (standardized)
genesis 3:6 [gottingen]

καὶ εἶδεν ἡ γυνὴ ὅτι καλὸν τὸ ξύλον εἰς βρῶσιν, καὶ ὅτι ἀρεστὸν τοῖς ὀφθαλμοῖς ἰδεῖν καὶ
ὠραῖόν ἐστιν τοῦ κατανοῆσαι, καὶ λαβοῦσα τοῦ καρποῦ αὐτοῦ ἔφαγεν· καὶ ἔδωκεν καὶ τῷ
ἀνδρὶ αὐτῆς μετ' αὐτῆς, καὶ ἔφαγον.

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ εἶδεν ἡ γυνὴ ὅτι καλὸν τὸ ξύλον εἰς βρῶσιν καὶ ὅτι ἀρεστὸν τοῖς ὀφθαλμοῖς
ἰδεῖν καὶ ὠραῖόν ἐστιν τοῦ κατανοῆσαι, καὶ λαβοῦσα τοῦ καρποῦ αὐτοῦ ἔφαγεν· καὶ
ἔδωκεν καὶ τῷ ἀνδρὶ αὐτῆς μετ' αὐτῆς, καὶ ἔφαγον.

Scores: 0.852, 0.606 (normalized), 9.030 (standardized)
proverbs 26:26 [rahlfs]

εδρίοις.

Scores: 0.818, 0.575 (normalized), 8.369 (standardized)

Query 3: Nonnus Panopolitanus, Paraphrasis sancti evangelii Joannei, I 1-3 : Ἄχρονος ἦν,
ἀκίχητος, ἐν ἀρρητῷ λόγος ἀρχῆ καὶ λόγος αὐτοφύτιο θεοῦ φάος, ἐκ φάεος φῶς

John 1:1 [nestle-aland-28]

Ἐν ἀρχῇ ἦν ὁ λόγος, καὶ ὁ λόγος ἦν πρὸς τὸν θεόν, καὶ θεὸς ἦν ὁ λόγος.

Scores: 2.927, 1.000 (normalized), 6.161 (standardized)

Acts 7:17 [nestle-aland-28]

Καθὼς δὲ ἤγγιζεν ὁ χρόνος τῆς ἐπαγγελίας ἧς ὠμολόγησεν ὁ θεὸς τῷ Ἀβραάμ, ἠΰξησεν ὁ λαὸς καὶ ἐπληθύνθη ἐν Αἰγύπτῳ

Scores: 2.801, 0.956 (normalized), 5.842 (standardized)

psalms 105:48 [gottingen]

Εὐλογητὸς κύριος ὁ θεὸς Ἰσραηλ ἀπὸ τοῦ αἰῶνος καὶ ἕως τοῦ αἰῶνος. καὶ ἐρεῖ πᾶς ὁ λαὸς Γένοιτο, γένοιτο.

Scores: 2.770, 0.946 (normalized), 5.764 (standardized)

psalms 105:48 [rahlfs]

Εὐλογητὸς κύριος ὁ θεὸς Ἰσραηλ ἀπὸ τοῦ αἰῶνος καὶ ἕως τοῦ αἰῶνος. καὶ ἐρεῖ πᾶς ὁ λαὸς Γένοιτο γένοιτο. —

Scores: 2.770, 0.946 (normalized), 5.764 (standardized)

1Tim 6:13 [nestle-aland-28]

παραγγέλλω [σοι] ἐνώπιον τοῦ θεοῦ τοῦ ζωογονοῦντος τὰ πάντα καὶ Χριστοῦ Ἰησοῦ τοῦ μαρτυρήσαντος ἐπὶ Ποντίου Πιλάτου τὴν καλὴν ὁμολογίαν,

Scores: 2.708, 0.924 (normalized), 5.607 (standardized)

genesis 14:19 [gottingen]

καὶ εὐλόγησεν τὸν Ἀβραὰμ καὶ εἶπεν Εὐλογημένος Ἀβραὰμ τῷ θεῷ τῷ ὑψίστῳ, ὃς ἔκτισεν τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ τὴν γῆν,

Variants:

[R_LXX] καὶ ἠλόγησεν τὸν Αβραμ καὶ εἶπεν Εὐλογημένος Αβραμ τῷ θεῷ τῷ ὑψίστῳ, ὃς ἔκτισεν τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ τὴν γῆν,

Scores: 2.698, 0.921 (normalized), 5.582 (standardized)

judith 13:17 [gottingen]

καὶ ἐξέστη πᾶς ὁ λαὸς σφόδρα καὶ κύψαντες προσεκύνησαν τῷ θεῷ καὶ εἶπαν ὁμοθυμαδὸν Εὐλογητὸς εἶ, ὁ θεὸς ἡμῶν ὁ ἐξουδενώσας ἐν τῇ ἡμέρᾳ τῇ σήμερον τοὺς ἐχθροὺς τοῦ λαοῦ σου.

Scores: 2.689, 0.918 (normalized), 5.560 (standardized)

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your first query .1

A: 2.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your second query .1

A: 1.0

Q: Please rate the overall quality of the results of your third query .1

A: 3.0

Q: Did the model return semantically relevant results, even if not literal matches? Did it do so among the top 5, 10 or 15 results?

A: No, after the first 15 results

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A: Yes, he made me proposals that I hadn't identified and which in some cases are relevant.

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A: Yes, when it comes to queries on Nonno, neologisms are a problem; it doesn't identify the exact meaning of more formally searched words (dialectal or archaic variants, neologisms), and it can't identify synonyms among the solutions it suggests.

Q: How well do you think the model captures contextual meaning in Latin and Greek?

A: It is of little success if the form of the text becomes complex, as in the case of epic poetry.

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A: This aspect could be implemented, I don't think it's ever enough.

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A: Yes.

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results?

A: Sometimes, scores aren't easy to understand. Graphs are very helpful.

Q: Please describe your general impression of the tool.

A: It's fast and comprehensive, but I don't think it's very effective at identifying synonyms yet. The formal differences between the texts are crucial to the accuracy of the results. Could something be done about this during the machine training phase?

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A: Perhaps stylistic metadata (meter: dactylic hexameters)

Q: In which ways do you think this model could enrich your research work?

A: It can help me find new connections with biblical texts implicit in a particular text such as a poetic paraphrase.

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A: I would enhance its stylometric capabilities, making it more adaptable to formally diverse texts, such as poetic ones; I would improve its linguistic capabilities (in Greek, the ability to recognize dialectal variants...).

Q: Which improvements would you propose to extend the scope of the model and scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A: I don't know, perhaps a graphical interface that makes its use and advantages immediately evident.

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool?

A: yes

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions:

A: nothing

9.2. *uBIQUity* - Arabic Tool Test (WP8): Feedback Questionnaire

Note on Response Format: To avoid redundancy and keep the appendix concise, each general question is listed only once, followed by the three individual responses labeled as Answer 1, Answer 2, and Answer 3. In contrast, for queries involving practical tool testing—where each participant tested the system with their own input (e.g., a *ḥadīth*, a *tafsīr* excerpt, or a keyword)—both the question and each participant’s answer are presented individually. This allows for a clearer understanding of how different testers interacted with the tool.

Q: What digital tools do you currently use to analyze the Arabic sources you work on?

A1: Qwen VL72B; Google Vision AI; Kraken OCR; Diffusion models; Different LLMs, Transformers (AraBERT) and other hybrid solutions.

A2: al-Shamila.

A3: I do not use any specialized tools at the moment; my work primarily involves organizing and analyzing data using Excel spreadsheets.

Q: What are the main features you typically look for when working with digital tools for text analysis and text reuse?

A1: Consistency in output performance, reusability, language independence in multilingual contexts, semantic or other metadata output and their quality. Hence, from a more Humanist perspective, insights into possible new connection between and reuse in different texts over decades and centuries.

A2: The ability to search for quotations; support for Arabic script and morphology; export and citation.

A3: At this stage, I do not rely on specialized digital tools for text analysis or text reuse. My work is primarily conducted using structured Excel files. However, when considering digital tools for future use, I would prioritize features such as support for right-to-left scripts (especially Arabic), the ability to handle large textual datasets, reliable search and matching functions, and compatibility with metadata extraction workflows.

Q: Are you familiar with text reuse tools?

A1: Been at the Aga Khan University at the CDH center which developed and integrated the passim algorithm into the Kitab Project corpus they have previously built in the OpenITI frame. The passim system used in the text reuse case based on text alignment algorithm such as the Smith-Waterman. At the same time the CDH.

A2: No

A3: Yes

Q: What is your level of familiarity with AI-based technologies in the humanities?

A1: Expert

A2: Beginner

A3: Advanced

Q: Are you familiar with transformer-based models such as BERT?

A1: Use of BERT-based models fine-tuned for Arabic language such as araBERT for developing topic modeling solutions for cataloguing non-Latin and Islamic studies texts.

A2: No

A3: Yes

Q: We are now providing three preset queries. For each query, please:

- 1. Examine at least the first 10 results returned by the tool, in the order in which they appear.**
- 2. Rate the overall relevance of the results on a scale from 1 to 4.**
- 3. Provide a brief explanation of your rating.**

Query 1:

إن القرآن أنزل على سبعة أحرف فاقرؤوا منه ما تيسر

(From *Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī, Kitāb al-Khuṣūmāt*)

How relevant were the results returned by the tool?

A1: Mostly relevant

A2: Mostly relevant

A3: Mostly relevant

Q: Please explain your rating for Query 1. Did the tool return semantically relevant results, even if they were not literal matches? Did relevant results appear among the top 5, 10, or 15?

A1: Results are returned, and not all are only exact matching but also paragraphs with semantic relevance and close to the hadith searched are outputted which is a good result. Semantic similarity provided and ranked in a proper way. Reducing the top k retrieved passages to 15, 10 or even less will output the most similar in decreasing order.

A2: I chose ‘mostly relevant’ because the first result wasn’t complete. In result 1 the author’s name is missing even if it appears in the ‘filename’ (Nizam al-din al-Nisaburi). I found the author’s birth date (650 H. /1253 C. E.?), also missing, and other biographical information in the following sources: VIAF (Virtual International Authority File); English Wikipedia; al-Kindi Catalogue. In result 2 we found a lot of precise information, but a little bit confused in second part of section ‘inf’: in this section the tool quotes many sources to demonstrate that the work belongs to the author, but this info is not too relevant for our search. The third result is correct, and we verified the info on Shamila. All the results appear in the correct chronological order.

A3: I assigned a rating of 3 (Mostly Relevant). The tool successfully retrieved several results that are either exact matches or semantically equivalent paraphrases of the hadith: “إن هذا القرآن أنزل على سبعة أحرف فاقرؤوا منه ما تيسر”. These include narrations from major hadith collections such as Ṣaḥīḥ Ibn Ḥibbān, Sunan Abī Dāwūd, and al-Mustakhraj ‘alā Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim, which appeared within the top 5 results.

Query 2:

وكان سبب ذلك أن الجن كانت تسترق السمع فلما حرست السماء ورجموا بالشهب قال إبليس إن هذا الذي حدث في السماء لشيء حدث في الأرض

(From *Tafsīr al-Tha‘labī*)

A1: Mostly relevant

A2: Mostly relevant

A3: Very relevant

Q: Please explain your rating for Query 2. Did the tool return semantically relevant results, even if they were not literal matches? Did relevant results appear among the top 5, 10, or 15?

A1: Same as the first case, however as expected the reuse of longer sentences with different semantics meaning and the intrinsic polysemy of many of the terms involved cause the similarity score to drop significantly. Nonetheless, the output is fundamentally sound in every case of top k retrieved passages.

A2: Result 1: the author's name is not complete (Abu Hafs Umar ibn Ali ibn Adil al-Dimashqi al-Hanbali) and the birth date is missing (675 H. / 1276 CE). Result 2 contains a mistake: the last highlighted sentence occurs twice (see al-Shamila) and the last word is incomplete. Result 3 is correct except for the death date in Gregorian calendar (965 instead of 944-45). Result 4 repeats result 3. The chronological order of the sources is reversed.

A3: Although the tool did not return any exact textual matches for the query, it retrieved several passages that were highly semantically relevant. Relevant results appeared consistently within the top 5 and top 10.

Query 3:

الدجال

A1: Mostly relevant

A2: Slightly relevant

A3: Very relevant

Q: Please explain your rating for Query 3. Did the tool return semantically relevant results? Did relevant results appear among the top 5, 10, or 15?

A1: A single word of course will find many matches and reuse case on several text. Here semantic similarity is hard to define since different passages with different contexts happen to have the same word inside and as imaginable the similarity is like the previous drop staying around 0.68 to 0.58. Results are relevant and related to the single word sentence even though contexts are different.

A2: The results are semantically relevant, except the result 4 where the query does not appear at all. Anyway, the criterion used in the choice of sources is unclear. They seem to have been chosen at random. For ex., the first quotation is taken from the collection of hadith by Abu Dawud, which is not the most relevant, as the query is also present in Bukhari and Muslim. Another example: in the second result Razi's tafsir has been chosen, but why not Tabari, Ibn Kathir or Zamakhshari? The result 4 pick up the word in a non-canonical source (al-Tabarani).

A3: The tool returned strong results on the topic of al-Dajjāl, including canonical hadith and narrative or eschatological discussions. However, not all top 10 results are equally focused or relevant. Relevant results appeared among the top 5 (especially Results 1, 2, and 5). Results (6–9) were highly relevant.

Interviewee 1

Q: You may now test the tool using three queries of your choice. Feel free to select a passage, an expression, and a keyword from your research (e.g., a ḥadīth, a tafsīr excerpt, and a specific term), and evaluate how well the tool retrieves relevant results. Please write here your first query and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A1:

رجعنا من الجهاد الأصغر إلى الجهاد الأكبر

Score of similarity is rather low even though the semantic output is correct and relevant in most cases including from exact matching to more articulate semantic contexts. I think the tool in this sense is functional to providing same passages through different textual traditions and outlining eventual reuse cases. Note also that this hadith is considered by most studies as not Sahih.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your first query?

A1: Mostly relevant

Q: Please write your second query and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A1:

حديث عبد الله بن عمرو بن العاص رضي الله عنهما أن رسول الله صلى الله عليه وسلم قال: "إن الله لا يقبض العلم انتزاعًا ينتزعه من العباد، ولكن يقبض العلم بقبض العلماء، حتى إذا لم يبق عالم اتخذ الناس رؤوسًا جهالًا، فسئلوا فأفتوا بغير علم، فضلوا وأضلوا"

Similarity score, results and top k ranking seems to work properly on this query, pretty much as done in the others.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your second query?

A1: Very relevant

Q: Please write your third query (a single keyword), and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A1:

أمانة

Results were relevant, in this case most of them related to Arabic dictionaries (general or qur'anic ones). Basically, the tool behaved as did in the single keyword of the third query in the first section.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your third query?**A1:** Mostly relevant**Interviewee 2**

Q: You may now test the tool using three queries of your choice. Feel free to select a passage, an expression, and a keyword from your research (e.g., a ḥadīth, a tafsīr excerpt, and a specific term), and evaluate how well the tool retrieves relevant results. Please write here your first query and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A2:

صُمِّمَ مِنَ الشَّهْرِ ثَلَاثَةَ أَيَّامٍ، قَالَ: أَطِيبُ أَكْثَرَ مِنْ ذَلِكَ، فَمَا زَالَ حَتَّى قَالَ: صُمِّمَ يَوْمًا وَأَفْطِرُ يَوْمًا، فَقَالَ: اقْرَأِ الْقُرْآنَ فِي كُلِّ شَهْرٍ، قَالَ: إِنِّي أَطِيبُ أَكْثَرَ، فَمَا زَالَ حَتَّى قَالَ: فِي ثَلَاثِ

We choose a hadith from the Sahih of Bukhari. The tool didn't recognize the original source (Bukhari) and the first two results are variants taken from the same source: Abu Dawud, which is another canonical source. The other results are selected from non-canonical sources (Ibn Habban, Ibn Farra' al-Baghawi, al-Maturidi). Also in this case, the criterion for selecting the sources is not clear.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your first query?**A2:** Slightly relevant

Q: Please write your second query and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A2:

قال، حدثنا إسحاق قال، حدثنا عبد الله، عن ورقاء، عن ابن أبي نجيح، عن مجاهد، في قوله: (وأوحينا إليه لتنبئهم بأمرهم هذا وهم لا يشعرون) قال: أوحى إلى يوسف وهو في الجب أن سينبئهم بما صنعوا، وهم لا يشعرون بذلك الوحي

The second query was selected from Ṭabarī's tafsīr (Q 12:15). The tool does not recognize the source from which the passage was taken (Ṭabarī) and does not select other tafsirs

which quote Ṭabarī himself. The first result is by an Ibadite author (al-Hawarī). The second result is taken from Maturīdī's tafsīr. The third result is taken from a Shiite tafsīr (al-Tūsī); the fourth result is also taken from a Shiite tafsīr (al-Tabarsi). The latter appears closer to Ṭabarī's text than the previous ones. It seems that the tool prefers to select the same authors, in particular al-Maturidi.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your second query?

A2: Slightly relevant

Q: Please write your third query (a single keyword), and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A2:

جبريل

Third query, result 1. The results are fairly relevant as they are all drawn from tafsir works. The first result once again draws from the tafsir of Ibn 'Ādil. The evaluation of this result is the same as the one provided for the first result of the second preset query. Result two draws from the tafsir of Zayd ibn 'Alī, for whom the date of birth is omitted, while the conversion of the death date to the Gregorian calendar is incorrect (122 AH = 740 CE). The highlighted sentence begins with a truncated word. The same sentence is repeated on the following line: the extraction process from Shamela is not functioning correctly. Result 3. The text is taken from the tafsir of Ibn Ḥamza al-Qurra al-Kirmānī. The dates provided by the tool — only the death dates — are incorrect (cf. al-Kindī: 450–535 AH / 1058–1140 CE). Here too, the sources are not ordered according to any chronological principle. Also, the criteria for source selection are unclear — both regarding the tafsir sources and the absence of citation of the primary source, which is the Qur'an itself.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your third query?

A2: Mostly relevant

Interviewee 3

Q: You may now test the tool using three queries of your choice. Feel free to select a passage, an expression, and a keyword from your research (e.g., a ḥadīth, a tafsīr excerpt, and a specific term), and evaluate how well the tool retrieves relevant results. Please write here your first query and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A3:

رسائل ابن رشد الطبية (book title)

To test whether the tool can retrieve bibliographic or content-related results (e.g., metadata, ISBN, or excerpts) associated with Ibn Rushd’s medical writings. Only a few vague thematic connections. No direct matches, no bibliographic metadata, and no occurrences of the query string or expected result.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your first query?

A3: Not relevant

Q: Please write your second query and comment on the first results returned by the tool

A3:

يا رسول الله كيف يأتيك الوحي

The tool successfully retrieved multiple relevant results that match or paraphrase the well-known hadith in which al-Ḥārith ibn Hishām asked the Prophet ﷺ how revelation came to him.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your second query?

A3: Mostly relevant

Q: Please write your third query (a single keyword), and comment on the first results returned by the tool.

A3:

ردمك (Arabic acronym for ISBN)

Despite using the standardized Arabic term for ISBN, none of the top 10 results retrieved by the tool contain ISBN numbers.

Q: How relevant were the results returned by the tool for your third query?

A3: Not relevant

Q: How intuitive did you find the tool’s interface? (1 = Not intuitive; 4 = Very intuitive)

A1: 3

A2: 3

A3: 3

Q: How would you improve the tool's interface?

A1: The tool interface is easy to use and understand though still in a prototypical form. Filters could be improved by simplifying possible choices. Most of the filters which are related to the metadata do not provide any indication on what they are and at this stage are the same used in the Kitab project. Filters should be displayed better and more importantly they should be reordered keeping the same order for every page and every corpus. A bit of normalization on that point would enhance clarity and cleanliness of the UI. Metadata provided in the output are heavy and could confuse the reader. To find where a passage is in the original file or printed text (in the case of the OpenITI corpus is about Shamela or Shia online eventually) the user must look across all the metadata for every passage which is not a problem by itself if used one or twice. However, if use is extensive that visual representation of the output should be enhanced. Metadata of every single work taken from the OpenITI corpus or others should be placed in separate section or page and openly linked to the original *corpora*.

A2: Greater accuracy in the selection of sources is needed, clearly stating the criteria used for their selection. As for the results, they should be ordered according to the intended objectives: if the goal is to identify a ḥadīth, the search should start with the canonical sources, considered the most authentic, and then proceed to the secondary ones.

A3: Implement an interactive query builder with structured input fields: Book Title Author Keyword/Phrase Metadata fields (e.g., ISBN, subject heading, publication year).

Q: Did you encounter any difficulties interpreting the results? (1 = Very difficult to interpret; 4 = Easy to interpret)

A1: 3

A2: 4

A3: 3

Q: Describe your general impressions of the tool.

A1: Tool is functional and provides results that are in line with queries and with semantic similarities of the passages.

A2: The tool certainly has significant potential, but it needs to be improved in line with the recommendations provided in the previous point.

A3: The tool’s semantic search and metadata extraction capabilities across Arabic-script sources seem promising.

Q: Did you find the results meaningful in your area of expertise?

A1: It is meaningful and helpful to understand intertextual connections, reuse and retrieve information needed that are scholarly checked (which is important to avoid also not controlled knowledge retrieval patterns that can be dangerous especially in the context of religious studies). However, it should be remarked that results must be shown in a more user-scholar friendly visualization. As said, metadata in the output could be reduced to a bibliographic reference (author, title, researcher/editor, year, publishing house, volume, page - that should suffice to provide the researcher meaningful info) and then every output could be linked to the original corpus metadata in a corresponding page or section of the *uBIQUity* tool User Interface.

A2: No answer

A3: The results were partially meaningful for the intended tasks within the field of digital Islamic studies and Arabic-script book metadata extraction, though there are notable limitations.

Q: Did you notice any errors or inconsistencies in the suggested results? If yes, please describe them.

A1: Not really, in few cases the highlighted section was less relevant than other parts of the same passage, but it happened very rarely.

A2: Sometimes the tool doesn’t copy correctly the quotation.

A3: No answer

Q: How well do you think the tool captures contextual meaning in Arabic? (1 = Poorly; 4 = Very well)

A1: 3

A2: 4

A3: 3

Q: Do you think the amount of surrounding context provided is sufficient to understand the reuse?

A1: It depends mostly on the type of query but in general the tool did a good job.

A2: It depends on the submitted query.

A3: Yes

Q: Did you find the metadata below each result useful and clear?

A1: Not useful except for some that should be kept (as said, those that are useful to referencing and to find the passage in the original source). The rest of the metadata follows the scheme of another project which developed their own personal metadata scheme in compliance with the wider initiative they work on. Using the same is surely useful but most of the metadata is not clear enough for users not in contact with those realities.

A2: Not always.

A3: No

Q: Would you suggest adding other types of metadata? If yes, which ones?

A1: No less metadata in the tool interface and those present in a specific page or menu or section linked to the original sources. The point is not adding, is visually simplifying, normalize and pay attention also to other metadata standard (Dublin core etc.)

A2: I don't know.

A3: Yes. Include both Hijri and Gregorian dates of publication and author's death. Adding the ability to restrict or target queries to a specific website or digital library, such as Shamela.

Q: In what ways do you think this tool could enrich your research work?

A1: It gives the researchers the chance to connect texts from their textual features, study reuse cases in a very useful and quick way, the filter if simplified could help the researcher to select specific texts for specific needs, as well as the serendipitous opportunity to find new unseen connections and extend knowledge by posing other research questions.

A2: In searching for quotations easily.

A3: It can be used to locate recurring topical headers, manual tables of contents, or subject keywords within full-text digital books (e.g., from Shamela).

Q: What improvements or additions would you suggest to make the tool more practical or useful for your specific research context?

A1: Those I have said before.

A2: No answer

A3: No answer

Q: Would you recommend this tool to a colleague in your field?

A1: Maybe

A2: Maybe

A3: Yes

Q: What improvements would you propose to improve the generalization of the tool so as to scale it to your colleagues' needs?

A1: Refine Transformer-based models on Arabic specific ontologies for religious studies to enhance possible semantic similarity in specific cases. However, this is more a general paradigm shift that should convoy all the under-represented languages in the training sets of those models.

A2: It should draw from the original sources and according to precise criteria of search.

A3: Researchers often rely on multiple platforms for full-text access and metadata. Add source-specific scraping modules or allow the tool to query directly from structured sources like Shamela.

Q: Do you think specific training should be offered along with the tool? (1 = Absolutely necessary; 4 = Not necessary)

A1: 2

A2: 1

A3: 3

Q: Please feel free to add any further observations, comments, or suggestions.

A1: Arabic Sources as *corpora* is not clear what contains and from where it is taken. Is there any overlap with the other corpus? Are they complementary? What kind of sources? tafasir, ahadith collections, jarh wa ta'dil, biographies, tarajim, tabaqat, fiqh, lexicography and 'ilm al-lughah?

A2: No answer

A3: No answer

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